

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Over the years, the financial performance of manufacturing companies has drawn a noticeable concern due to its capacity in causing a rapid economic prosperity around the world. The level of growth experienced by the manufacturing companies is capable of exerting significant influence on poverty alleviation through the creation of employment and increase in the standard of living of individuals and households alike (Dada, Kolapo & Mokuolu, 2021). Even though the sector possesses this capability, the growth of Nigeria's manufacturing companies has cascaded over the years. This depressing situation has long been demonstrated in the performance of Nigerian industries (Manufacturing Association of Nigeria, 2014).

Although the economy of Nigeria is characterized by numerous alarming activities including corruption, bad governance, bribery, lack of policy activation, inadequate infrastructural facilities and continuous or unusual competition slows down the pace of converting produced goods into cash and safeguarding the interest of investors in the company (Korode, 2017). The longevity of a firm relies significantly on its ability and efficiency in applying the components of financial management (Karaduman, 2018). Following this, adequate planning and working capital management is urgent in the bid to achieve good results despite the pressure from the increasingly competitive manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

All over the world, working capital is an all-important technique required by an organization to ensure adequate management of its resources as this determines the continuous existence of the business (Owolabi & Alu, 2018). Working capital is an extremely important aspect in

the structure of an organization; it requires an increased attention, control and proper planning. Considering the scarcity of resources available to organizations, it is expedient for an organization to critically manage its working capital as it plays a vital role in the attainment of attractive financial position and the general performance of the organization (Adeshola, 2022).

Working capital describes the fund kept in the form of materials, work in progress, finished goods, cash and receivables. In this way, Khan and Jain (2017) identified that current assets are those assets that can be turned into cash within an accounting period, and the cash received is again invested into these assets; therefore, causing a constant receipt of cash and reinvestment. This is been referred to as very essential in the existence of any business organization. This occasioned the quest for an optimal working capital management in all business firms.

The manufacturing sector maintains a vital position in the stabilization of economic activities and also represents a key driver in the goal of attaining economic growth and development through employment creation, increase exports; improve economic performance and sources of foreign exchange revenue (Korode, 2017). In the 70s and 80s, the manufacturing sector which the consumer goods sector forms a part, was ascertained to positively influence the Nigeria's economic output (GDP) by 11% and 9.9% respectively. Although an evident decline exists during the decade, the continuous fall in the degree of contribution was attributed to the low quality of working capital management, domination of foreign manufacturing companies, importation of products that can be produced locally among other issues (Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2012). In 2013, Manufacturers Association of Nigeria maintained that the manufacturing sector impacts the Nation's GDP by just 6%, this

drastic reduction is coupled with the fall in the industrial capacity usage of Nigeria manufacturing sectors which cascaded from 58% to 28%, this justifies the fact that numerous manufactured goods consumed in Nigeria are imported into the economy, this which leads to crowding out effect of the products of local industries and unsatisfactory management of working capital. Salawu and Alao (2014) corroborated in their study that in the first quarter of 2013, the manufacturing sector experienced a noticeable fall in its output, particularly from 7.03% in 2013 to 6.43 in 2014.

In Nigeria, local industries have over the years suffered from the atrocious infrastructural situation including the dilapidated state of infrastructural facilities, limited access to fund, security issues and increased finance costs paid by local manufacturing firms to their creditors, these and several other challenges have impeded the progress of the manufacturing goods companies (Oke & Adebola, 2022). Despite having to deal with these depressing situations especially the limited financial access to funds from ordinary and specialized financial institutions, firms have invented an alternative system to reaching funds to improve working capital. Most times, this is done through getting inventory and increasing the productive capacity to satisfy customers' needs (Korode, 2017). Hence, the need to adequately manage the working capital which involves controlling and financing the current assets of a firm is urgent especially in manufacturing companies. This is so because manufacturing companies undoubtedly owns huge investment in working capital assets and considering this, the effectiveness of these companies depends greatly on absolute financing and working capital management (Kehinde, 2020).

The average collection period (ACP) represents the length of time it takes the companies to collect proceeds of sales from their debtors (Uremadu, Egbide & Enyi, 2018). Accounts receivable which is the major component of ACP stands for the amount the consumers have to pay to the firm on a current basis and is related to the operating activities (Nuhiu & Dërmaku, 2017). When companies receive the payments from the customers close to the moment on which they deliver the product/service (Nuhiu & Dërmaku, 2017), such companies have more cash to be invested in the business for increased profitability. Thus it is expected that ACP has a negative impact on the financial returns of manufacturing goods companies in Nigeria. The average payment period (APP) is all about the average time taken between purchases of materials and using labour force and cash payments relating to them (Alipour, 2020). Accounts payable, which form the major component of the APP, are short term liabilities or amount payable for purchases made on credit (Iqbal et al., 2016). Companies with efficient WCM have the option of delaying payments to the suppliers most especially when cheap financing is available and then invest the cash and cash equivalents in other activities for higher financial returns (Nuhiu & Dërmaku, 2017). In this case, the prior expectation is positive.

The inventory turnover period (ITP) refers to the time taken to convert inventories held in the firm into sales (Mathuva, 2020). The frequency of the number of days inventories are converted into sales reflects in the profitability of a firm (Nuhiu & Dërmaku, 2017). Thus, it should be expected that the ITP negatively affects the company's financial returns. An important motive of WCM involves maximising time outflows and inflows of cash and cash equivalents which is known as the cash conversion cycle (CCC). Efforts must be made in any organisation to minimise the time between expenses for getting inventory and cash reception

resulted from selling it, because CCC comprehensively measures WCM (Oseifuah & Gyekye, 2016). CCC touches all aspects of the business that can ensure its smooth running by being sensitive to the internal resources, cost of external financing, capital market access and the bargaining power with suppliers and customers. Since a shorter CCC is a sign of efficient WCM, the impact of CCC on financial returns of manufacturing goods companies in Nigeria is expected to be negative.

Generally, working capital management beyond enhancing the financial performance of the unpromising and cash-strapped economy, the day to day operation of the firm needs to be examined. Hence, it is an urgent issue to ascertain and digest the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of manufacturing sector. However, despite the significance of the working capital issue and the interest of several researchers over time in Nigeria, an unimpressive attention is given to the impact of working capital management especially on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Based on this premise, this study sets out to assess the impact of working capital management on corporate financial performance of manufacturing goods companies in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Following the global economic failure, numerous listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group was grossly affected as their profitability position reduced drastically (Korode, 2017), several consumer goods manufacturing firms have since this period been struggling to remain in the market. The unfavourable operating environment characterized by numerous unfriendly infrastructural conditions has posed serious issues hindering the growth of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Despite these economic issues, the effectiveness of manufacturing companies is extremely influenced by the competence of financial managers

particularly in ensuring an effective control of working capital components of the firm (Yahaya, 2016).

Surprisingly, manufacturing goods companies have been faced with numerous liquidity issues triggered by the inability to settle short term commitments in several consumer goods industry (Solanke, Ahmed & Kabiru, 2019). This challenge is occasioned by the management's inability to control its working capital so as to reach the best and also improving the financial performance of the company (Vanessa & Cordelia, 2021). Consequently, several manufacturing goods companies are faced with problems concerning policies aimed at fast-tracking the collection period; this is accompanied with the unimpressive caution demonstrated by the firm towards the inventory levels (Otekunrin et al, 2021; Okoye, et al, 2020). These evident defects in the system of numerous manufacturing firms have negatively influenced the profitability of firms and also causing a gross reduction in the worth of companies.

Again, the inability of the manufacturing firms in Nigeria to adequately make plans and draw management techniques to capture the exigencies of working capital of their respective firms according to Korode (2017) called for concerned. The deficient working capital management resulting from the bad management has over the years been the cause of the loss of earnings to over or under-stocking, high bad debts, liquidity challenge, financial losses, low retained earnings, inability to expand, insolvency and defenceless management especially from liquidation (Osho & Nwankwo, 2018).

Furthermore, Ajayi, Abogun and Odediran (2017) identified that a significant portion of raw materials inputs employed by Nigerian manufacturing firms are usually imported, the process of import which is undoubtedly affected by the unstable foreign exchange market and

monetary policy of the government. The affected inventory of raw materials faced by the weaknesses of foreign exchange in the process of importation, delays in clearing at the Nigerian ports and the bad transportation facilities, these unarguably exerted a negative influence on the production process of manufacturing companies in Nigeria and the delivery of the products to customers (Abdul- Khadir, Abdul & Aliyu, 2020).

The increased finance cost charged by financial institutions in Nigeria have constrained manufacturing firms to short-term finance such as collection on sales, impeding growth in the net working capital. Hence, to further consolidate the performance of the manufacturing companies through an effectual management of working capital, this study aims at assessing the impact of working capital management on corporate financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective to this study is to examine the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study include:

1. To assess the effect of Average Collection Period (ACP) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
2. To determine the effect of Average Payment Period (APP) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
3. To ascertain the effect of Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

4. To evaluate the effect of Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

1.4 Research questions

From the above specific objectives to this study, the following research questions have been deduced:

1. What is the effect of Average Collection Period (ACP) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of Average Payment Period (APP) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria?
3. What is the effect of Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria?
4. What is the effect of Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria?

1.5 Research hypotheses

From the above research question, the following research hypotheses have been postulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Average Collection Period (ACP) and the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Average Payment Period (APP) and the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant between cash conversion cycle (CCC) and the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study examined the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This study will be beneficial to the following:

Management: This study is very crucial as it will give the financial managers of manufacturing companies in Nigeria a better insights on the need to pay particular attention to the effective and efficient management of their working capital. They will be in a better position to be able to design and implement strategies and policies that are aim at stabilizing and managing the various components of working capital especially as it significantly impact on the main aim of business which is creating shareholders' value. Also it will enable the management to know at what extend they should increase their liquidity in order to make their performance up to the mark. This is very important in improving the good will of their firms, since firms that pay creditors as at when due are considered credit worthy and gains a good reputation.

Researchers/Academics: And for the academic purposes, the research work will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on working capital management and firm's performance. Finally, it is expected that the study will serve as a source of information to students undergoing research work of this nature in the future.

Government: At the end of this study, government agencies like Manufacturing Association of Nigeria would see this study as an added material that is specifically targeted at helping manufacturing companies in Nigeria improve their organizational performance. More so, the

need for the government to ensure that policies that are favourable to these business owners should be considered and to ensure the provision of enabling business environment is given to the manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

1.7 Scope of the study

This study will explore the relationship between working capital management and financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The choice of this area of study is because manufacturing companies is a sector that have been faced with numerous liquidity issues triggered by the inability to settle short term commitments. The study covers a period of ten years (2014 - 2023) the choice of this period is because Nigeria experienced significant economic fluctuations during this period, including periods of economic growth and recession. Fluctuations in economic conditions impact the liquidity and profitability of manufacturing companies, making it essential to understand how working capital management practices influence financial performance in different economic environments. Also many manufacturing companies in Nigeria face resource constraints, including limited access to financing and challenges in managing working capital effectively. Understanding the relationship between working capital management and financial performance can help companies optimize their use of resources and improve profitability, especially during periods of economic uncertainty.

1.8 Operational definition of terms

Working Capital Management (WCM) is the management of the current assets and current liabilities of a firm in order to ensure that the firm has sufficient liquid assets to meet their current maturing obligations or liabilities.

Working Capital (WC) is the net difference between current assets and current liabilities of a business enterprise.

Debtors/ account receivables are amount to be received by the firm for goods sold to customers on a credit basis.

Average collection period (ACP) is the time interval it takes customers to whom goods and service have been sold to on a credit terms to settle their debt obligations to the firm.

Creditors/account payables are amount due to be paid by the firm for purchases made by them to the suppliers.

Average Payment Period (APP) is the time interval between when credit purchases are made and the time payment is actually made by the firm to the suppliers. Inventories are stock of goods such as raw material, work-in-progress, and finished goods which are waiting for sale.

Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) is the length of time it takes to transform inventories into debtors or cash.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) is the amount of days between when a firm collects proceeds from sales to debtors and when they actually settle their debt obligations to their creditors.

Liquidity is ability of a firm to adequately and continuously settle debt obligations as at when they fall due with the available cash.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses conceptual clarification, theoretical review, empirical review and gap in literature.

2.2 Conceptual Clarification

This subsection will discuss the concept of working capital, working capital management, objectives of working capital management, working capital management policies, working capital management in developing economies, average collection period, inventory turnover in days, average payment period, cash conversion cycle, organizational performance, return on assets, return on equity, return on investment and return on sales will be discussed and presented.

2.2.1 Working Capital

The term working capital originated with the old Yankee peddler, who would load up his wagon with goods and then go off on his route to peddle his wares. The merchandise was called working capital because it was what he actually sold, or “turned over,” to produce his profits. The wagon and horse were his fixed assets. He generally owned the horse and wagon, so they were financed with “equity” capital, but he borrowed the funds to buy the merchandise. These borrowings were called working capital loans, and they had to be repaid after each trip to demonstrate to the bank that the credit was sound. If the peddler was able to repay the loan, then the bank would make another loan, and banks that followed this procedure were said to be employing “sound banking practices” (Brigham & Houston, 2004).

The term working capital is commonly used for the capital required for day-to-day working in a business concern, such as for purchasing raw material, for meeting day-to-day expenditure on salaries, wages, rents rates, advertising and the like. But, still there is much disagreement among various financial authorities (Financiers, accountants, businessmen and economists) as to the exact meaning of the term working capital.

Working capital is defined by Brigham and Houston (2001), as the manner in which the permanent and temporary current assets of a firm are being financed. Ashiq (2011) sees working capital as the relative mix of short and long term funds in financing working capital. According to Li and Han-Wen (2006), working capital management involves the application of strategies and policies in the utilization of a firm's current assets and liabilities in such a way that an optimum level of working capital is maintained. In essence, the goal of working capital management is to promote a satisfying profitability and maximizes shareholders' value.

Haitham & Maryam (2005) define working capital as the funds locked up in materials, work in progress, finished goods, receivables, and cash and cash equivalent. Thus, they defined working capital as capital invested in current assets, which are those assets that can be converted into cash within a short period of time and the cash received is again invested into the assets. In the words of Ugochukwu, Stanley & Onyekwena (2014), Working Capital represents the amount of current assets that have not been supplied by current, short term creditors. In the same vein Snober, (2014) opined that working capital is the excess of current assets that has been supplied by the long-term creditors and the stockholders.

However, working capital is divided into Gross and net; Gross working capital refers to the amount of funds invested in current assets that are employed in the business process while,

Net Working Capital refers to the difference between current assets and current liabilities (Cyprian & Tobias, 2014). Moreover, Current assets and liabilities, that is, assets and liabilities with maturities of less than one year, need to be carefully managed. Net working capital is the term given to the difference between current assets and current liabilities: current assets may include inventories of raw materials, work-in-progress and finished goods, trade receivables, short term investments and cash, while current liabilities may include trade payables, overdrafts and short-term loans. The level of current assets is a key factor in a company's liquidity position (Juliano & William, 2014). Working capital can be viewed dynamically as equilibrium between the income-generating and resource-purchasing activities of a company (Zdenek, & Dana, 2014), in which case it is closely linked to the cash conversion cycle.

According to Chuan-guo Li, Hui-min, Shou & Yan (2014), Gross working capital (Total Current Assets) refer to the firm's investment in current assets. Current assets are the assets, which can be converted into cash within an accounting year or operating cycle. Thus, Gross working capital, is the total of all current assets. Net working capital according to them refers to the difference between current assets and current liabilities. Current liabilities are those claims of outsiders, which are expected to mature for payment within an accounting year. Net working capital may be positive or negative. A positive net working capital will arise when current assets exceed current liabilities and a negative net working capital will arise when current liabilities exceed current assets i.e. there is no working capital, but there is a working capital deficit. It includes therefore, the two concepts of working capital, gross working capital and net working capital which are exclusive; both are equally important for the efficient management of working capital (Joseph, Mercy & Simon, 2016).

The gross working capital focuses attention on two aspects; firstly, how to optimize investment in current assets and lastly; on how current assets is financed, while net working capital concept is qualitative. It indicates the liquidity position of the firm and suggests the extent to which working capital needs may be financed by permanent sources of funds (Olawale, 2014). Most businesses experience seasonal or cyclical fluctuations. For example, construction firms have peaks in the spring and summer, retailer's peak around Christmas, and manufacturers who supply both construction companies and retailers follow similar patterns. Similarly, all businesses must build up current assets when the economy is strong, but they then sell off inventories and reduce receivables when the economy slacks off. Hence, based on time, working capital may be classified into two important types namely; permanent and temporary working capital (Paramasivan & Subramanian, 2009) briefly discussed below:

Permanent Working Capital: It's also known as fixed working capital and it refers to a minimum amount of investment in all working capital which is required at all times to carry out minimum level of business activities (Brigham & Houston, 2003). In other words, it represents the current assets required on a continuing basis over the entire year. Furthermore, working capital has a limited life and usually not exceeding a year, in actual practice some part of the investment is always permanent. Since firms have relatively longer life and production does not stop at the end of a particular accounting period some investment is always locked up in the form of raw materials, work-in-progress, finished stocks, book debts and cash. Investment in these components of working capital is simply carried forward to the next year. This minimum level of investment in current assets that is required to continue the business without interruption is referred to as permanent working capital (Fabozzi & Peterson, 2003). It's financed through long term debt and common stock.

Temporary Working Capital: it's also known as the circulating or transitory working capital. This is the amount of investment required to take care of the fluctuations in the business activity. Fabozzi and Peterson (2003) define temporary working capital as a rise of working capital from seasonal fluctuations in a firm's business. Because firms do not have to maintain this form of working capital throughout in the year, or year after year, it may be better to use short-term (bank credit) rather than long-term sources of capital to satisfy temporary needs. In other words, it represents additional current assets required at different times during the operating year. For example, extra inventory has to be maintained to support sales during peak sales period (seasonal working capital). Similarly, receivable also increase and must be financed during period of high sales. On the other hand investment in inventories, receivables and the like will decrease in periods of depression (special working capital). Temporary working capital fluctuates over time with seasons and special needs of firm operations, whereas, permanent WC changes as firms sizes increases overtime. Furthermore, temporary WC is financed by short term debt.

The total working capital requirement of a firm is determined by a wide variety of factors. These factors affect different organizations differently and they also vary from time to time. In general factors influencing working capital decisions of a firm may be classified as two groups, such as internal factors and external factors (Paramasivan & Subramanian, 2009). The internal factor includes nature of business, size of business, firm's product policy, credit policy, and growth and expansion of business. The external factors include business fluctuations, changes in the technology, infrastructural facilities, import policy and the taxation policy. These factors are discussed in brief in the following lines: Internal factors: These are factors that the companies will take in to account while determining the optimal

level of working capital needed for the business concern by looking inherent factors related to the business and they are presented as follows:

Nature and size of the business: According to Paramasivan and Subramanian (2009), the working capital requirements of a firm are basically influenced by the nature and size of the business. Size may be measured in terms of the scale of operations. A firm with larger scale of operations will need more working capital than a small firm. Similarly, the nature of the business influences the working capital decisions. Trading and financial firms have less investment in fixed assets. But require a large sum of money to be invested in working capital. Retail stores, business units require larger amount of working capital, whereas, public utilities need less working capital and more funds to invest in fixed assets.

Firm's production policy: The firm's production policy (manufacturing cycle) is an important factor to decide the working capital requirement of a firm. The production cycle starts with the purchase and use of raw material and completes with the production of finished goods. On the other hand production policy is uniform production policy or seasonal production policy, also influences the working capital decisions. If the company maintains continues or uniform production policy, there is a need of regular working capital. If the production policy of the company depends upon the situation or conditions like season, working capital requirement will depend upon the conditions laid down by the company and changing demand (Paramasivan & Subramanian, 2009).

Firm's credit policy: According to Niman (2015), the credit policy of a firm influences credit policy of working capital. A firm following liberal credit policy to all customers requires funds. On the other hand, the firm adopting strict credit policy and grant credit facilities to few potential customers will require less amount of working capital.

Growth and expansion of business: Working capital requirement of a business firm tend to increase in correspondence with growth in sales volume and fixed assets. A growing firm may need funds to invest in fixed assets in order to sustain its growing production and sales (Niman, 2015). This will, in turn, increase investment in current assets to support increased scale of operations. Thus, a growing firm needs additional funds continuously.

External factors: According to Bayode and Adebisi (2012), sometime firm's working capital requirement can be affected by external factor which will not be controlled through the business internal administration and management process and they are discussed as follows:

Business fluctuations: Most firms experience fluctuations in demand for their products and services. These business variations affect the working capital requirements. When there is an upward swing in the economy, sales will increase, correspondingly, the firm's investment in inventories and book debts will also increase (Ezejiofor, Adigwe, & John-Akamelu, 2015). Under boom, additional investment in fixed assets may be made by some firms to increase their productive capacity. This act of the firm will require additional funds. On the other hand when, there is a decline in the economy, sales will come down and consequently, the condition will compare the firm to reduce their short-term borrowings. Similarly, the seasonal fluctuations may also affect the requirement of working capital of a firm.

Changes in the technology: Niman (2015) observe that the technological changes and developments in the area of production can have immediate effects on the need for working capital. If the firm wishes to install a new machine in the place of an old system, the new system can utilize less expensive raw materials, the inventory needs may be reduced thereby working capital needs may be affected.

Taxation policy: The amount of tax to be paid is determined by the prevailing tax regulations and very often taxes have to be paid in advance. Hence, the tax policies of the Government will influence the working capital decisions (Niman, 2015). According to Niman (2015), if the Government follows regressive taxation policy, i.e. imposing heavy tax burdens on business firms, they are left with very little profits for distribution and retention purpose. Consequently, the firm will have to borrow additional funds to meet their increased working capital needs. When there is a liberalized tax policy, the pressure on working capital requirement is minimized. In general, if tax liability increases, it will lead to an increase in the level of working capital and vice versa. In summary, firm's financial manager should have to take in to account the above determinants while deciding on the optimal level of working capital needed and the timing for day to day activities of the business operations.

2.2.1 Working Capital Management

In order to understand the importance of working capital one has to understand the working capital cycle which is described as the core for working capital management. Arnold (2008) said that working capital cycle includes all the major dimensions of business operations. It is quite clear that a bad management of a single account in this cycle might cause a big trouble for the non-living entity which might leads to its death. Therefore, the management of working capital and balance between components of working capital is extremely important for the smooth running of business. Similarly, the basic aim of financial management is to maximize the wealth of the shareholders and in order to achieve this; it is necessary to generate sufficient sales and profit.

However, sales do not convert in to cash instantly. The time between purchase of inventory items (raw material or merchandise) for the production and their conversion into cash is

known as operating cycle or working capital cycle. Therefore, working capital management deals with the act of planning, organizing and controlling the components of working capital (current asset and liability) like cash, bank balance, inventory, receivables, payables, overdraft and short term loans (Paramasivan & Subramanian, 2009). Abdul & Mohamed, (2007) defined working capital management as the process of dealing with the problems that arise in attempting to manage the current asset, current liabilities and the interrelationship that exists between them. Whereas, Mian and Talat (2010), note that working capital management is the administration of the whole aspects of both current assets and current liabilities.

Working capital management is a managerial accounting strategy focusing on maintaining efficient levels of both components of working capital (that is, current assets and current liabilities) in respect to each other (Robert, Mark & Rabih, 2011). Working capital management ensures that a company has sufficient cash flow in order to meet its short-term debt obligations and operating expenses. Implementing an effective working capital management system is an excellent way for many companies to improve their earnings, (Erik & Herbert, 2010). The two main aspects of working capital management are ratio analysis and management of individual components of working capital. Ratio analysis helps the management to identify areas of focus, such as inventory management, cash management, accounts receivable and payables management.

Working capital management involves, the process of managing the activities and processes related to working capital (Vedavinayagam, 2010). The aim is to ensure that there are checks and balances to ensure that the amount of cash flowing into the business is enough to sustain the company's operations. This must be an ongoing process that must be evaluated using the current level of assets and liabilities. Working capital management may involve

implementing short- term decisions that may or may not carry over from one financial period to the next, (Kesseven, 2006).

Kulkanya (2012) define working capital management as the administration of current assets in the name of cash, marketable securities, receivables and staff advances, and inventories. Adina (2010), demonstrates that good working capital management must ensure an acceptable relationship between the different components of a firm's working capital so as to make an efficient mix, which will guarantee capital adequacy. Therefore, working capital management should make sure that the desirable quantities of each component of the working capital are available for management.

Working capital management is defined by Kehinde (2011), as the management of investment in current assets and the financing of the current assets, and involves setting working capital management policy and carrying out that policy in a business's daily operations, to achieves its goals and objectives, such as shareholder wealth maximization, Competitive advantage, and growth. Working capital management in view of Ashiq Ali (2011) based on purpose of working capital ensures the effective and efficient utilization of the business's investment in fixed assets. According to Kehinde (2011), if performance criteria such as liquidity, solvency/bankruptcy, efficiency, profitability and Economic Value Added are considered, it will be clearly apparent that the business must hold and manage the different levels of working capital which are appropriate to its performance criteria. Sharma and Satish (2011), see working capital management from efficiency perspective and can be measured and achieved through the cash conversion efficiency, days operating cycle and days working capital.

2.2.1.1 Components of Working Capital

According to Razali and Naji, (2015), the necessary components of an organization's working capital, basically, depend on the type of business and industry. They further narrate that Cash, debtors, receivables, inventories, marketable securities, and redeemable futures can be recognized as the common components of organization's working capital. However, the question is to recognize the factors that determine the adequacy of working capital based on growth, size, operating cash flow, etc. The inability to understand the determining factors and measurement of adequate amounts of working capital will lead an organization to bankruptcy.

David (2010) provide the analysis of the components of gross working capital, which is the current assets, which can be converted into cash within an accounting year or operating cycle. Thus, Gross working capital, is the total of all current assets and includes; Inventories (Raw materials and Components, Work-in-Progress, Finished Goods, Others); Trade Debtors; Loans and Advance; Cash and Bank Balances; Bills Receivables; and Short-term Investment. On the other hand, Net Working Capital refers to the difference between current assets and current liabilities; where current liabilities are those claims of outsiders, which are expected to mature for payment within an accounting year (Deloof, 2003).

According to David (2010), net working capital may be positive or negative. A positive net working capital will arise when current assets exceed current liabilities and a negative net working capital will arise when current liabilities exceed current assets i.e. there is no working capital, but there is a working capital deficit. It includes; Trade Creditors; Bills Payable; Accrued or Outstanding Expenses; Trade Advances; Short Term Borrowings (Commercial Banks and Others); Provisions; and Bank Overdraft.

2.2.1.2 Objectives of Working Capital Management

One of the modern systems of corporate governance is management by objective that is all the organizational activities should be focused on the firm objectives. However, to be effective, working capital management requires a clear specification of the objectives to be achieved. The two main objectives of working capital management are to increase the profitability of a company and to ensure that it has sufficient liquidity to meet short-term obligations as they fall due and so continue in business (Pedro & Pedro 2012). Profitability is related to the goal of shareholder wealth maximization, so investment in current assets should be made only if an acceptable return is obtained.

Haitham and Maryam (2013) asserted that while liquidity is needed for a company to continue in business, a company may choose to hold more cash than is needed for operational or transaction needs, for example for precautionary or speculative reasons. The twin goals of profitability and liquidity will often conflict since liquid assets give the lowest returns. Cash kept in a safe will not generate a return, for example, while a six-month bank deposit will earn interest in exchange for loss of access for the six-month period.

2.2.1.3 Management of Working Capital Components

The basic working capital components which should be managed efficiently includes the account receivables or debtors collection period, accounts payables or creditors payment period, inventory management, cash and cash equivalents and the operating cycle of a firm. Accounts Receivables Management: This constitutes the management of firms' debtors. Accounts receivables period is the average time taken by credit customers to settle their accounts. Van (2004) stated that, since the purpose of offering credit are to maximize

profitability; the costs of debt collection should not be allowed to exceed the amounts recovered. More so, a company should prepare regularly aged trade receivables analysis and take steps to chase late payers. It is helpful to establish clear procedures for chasing late payers, to set out the circumstances under which credit control staff should send out reminders and initiate legal proceedings. Some thought could also be given to charging interest on overdue accounts to encourage timely payment, depending on the likely response of customers (Van & Wachowicz, 2004).

In working capital management, the receivables are a very important component of current assets and debtors collection period or receivables turnover in days which is the average length of time required to convert the firm's receivables into cash (Raheman, Qayyum & AFza, 2011). They added that managerial efficiency in granting and controlling credit could be ascertained on the basis of receivables turnover in days. It would indicate the pattern of debtors on the basis of which liquidity of debtors could be ascertained. If the firm takes more time in collecting receivables, the profitability of the firm declines. To make a sensible decision about whether to trade with a company or not, information about the business is needed. The risk of bad debts can be minimized if the creditworthiness of new customers is carefully assessed before credit is granted and if the creditworthiness of existing customers is reviewed on a regular basis. Relevant information can be obtained from a variety of sources. New customers can be asked to provide bank references to confirm their financial standing, and trade references to indicate satisfactory conduct of business affairs (Padachi, 2006).

Published information, such as the audited annual report and accounts of a prospective customer, may also provide a useful indication of creditworthiness. A company's own experience of similar companies would also be useful in forming a view on creditworthiness,

as will the experience of other companies within a group. For a fee, a report may be obtained from a credit reference agency, the credit report may include a company profile, recent accounts, financial ratios and industry comparisons, analysis of trading history, payment trends, types of borrowing, previous financial problems and a credit limit (Van & Wachowicz, 2004). Bearing in mind the cost of assessing creditworthiness, the magnitude of likely regular sales could be used as a guide to determine the depth of the credit analysis.

Moreover, a company's credit management policy should help it maximize expected profits (Van & Wachowicz, 2004). It would need to take into account its current and desired cash position, as well as its ability to satisfy expected demand. To put the credit management policy into effect successfully, managers and staff may need training or new staff may need to be recruited. Hence, the Key variables affecting the level of receivables will be the terms of sale prevailing in a company's area of business and the ability of the company to match and service comparable terms of sale. There is also a relationship between the level of receivables and a company's pricing policy: for example, it may choose to keep selling prices relatively high while offering attractive terms for early payment. The effectiveness of trade receivables follow up procedures used will also influence the overall level of receivables and the likelihood of bad debts arising (Van & Wachowicz, 2004).

The accounts receivables management policy formulated by senior managers should also take into account the administrative costs of debt collection, the ways in which the policy could be implemented effectively, and the costs and effects of easing credit (Van & Wachowicz, 2004). It should balance the benefits to be gained from offering credit to customers against the costs of doing so. Longer credit terms may increase turnover, but will also increase the risk of bad debts. The cost of increased bad debts and the cost of any additional working

capital required should be less than the increased profits generated by the higher turnover. In order to operate its trade receivables policy, a company needs to set up a credit analysis system, a credit control system and a trade receivables collection system. Hence, accounts receivables management is measured by the accounts receivable turnover ratio.

The Accounts receivables Turnover ratio is also termed as Debtors speed ratio. It indicates the quickness in realization of sundry debtors (Deloof (2003) & Padachi (2006)). The main object of this ratio is to know how much credit time is allowed and capital blocked in debtors. Debtors' turnover ratio also shows the effectiveness in collection of debts due. Generally, higher ratio is the indication of efficient management of liquidity. However, a firm should maintain a balance between the debtors outstanding and the amount of interest incurred on the blocked funds. The account receivables collection period is computed by dividing account receivables by net sales multiplied by 365 days (Raheman, 2011).

Accounts Payables Management: The accounts or trade payables deferral period is the average time taken by a company to pay its trade payables, i.e. its suppliers (Uyar, 2009). Current liabilities include all obligations, which mature within a year such as creditors, bills payable, accrued expenses, short-term bank loan, income tax liability and long-term debt excluding bank overdraft, all of which quickly mature in the current year. Uyar, (2009) opined that, accounts payables or Creditors Turnover ratio is used to know how much of credit time received by the firm from its trade creditors. Creditors' turnover ratio shows the breathing time received by the firm in terms of payment of credit purchase. Hence, the effectiveness lies in whether the firm is enjoying the actual credit period promised by suppliers. It is calculated by dividing the amount of purchases by creditors. Here it has been assumed that all of the purchases have been made as credit purchases. The account payables

period is computed by dividing account payables by net purchases multiplied by 365 days (Raheman, 2011).

Inventory Management: Inventory turnover in days is another important component of working capital management which is also called as inventory conversion period (Raheman, 2011). According to Aminu and Zainudin (2015), it is the average time required to convert materials into finished goods and then to sell those goods. This variable helps in evaluating the efficiency in inventory management policy of the firm. If the firms take more time in selling inventory which means inventories are not getting convert into sales, will decrease the profitability of firm. Inventory Turnover in Days is calculated using inventory divided by the cost of sales multiplied by 365 days.

Cash Management: According to Van (2004) there are three reasons why companies choose to hold cash. These are Transactions motive, precaution motive, and speculation motive. Transaction Motive, companies need a cash reserve in order to balance short-term cash inflows and outflows since these are not perfectly matched. This is called the transactions motive for holding cash, and the approximate size of the cash reserve can be estimated by forecasting cash inflows and outflows and by preparing cash budgets. In addition to the cash reserve held for day-to-day operational needs, cash may be built up to meet significant anticipated cash outflows, for example those arising from investment in a new project or the redemption of debt (Van, 2004). Precautionary motive, Van (2004) states that, forecasts of future cash flows are subject to uncertainty and it is possible that a company will experience unexpected demands for cash. This gives rise to the precautionary motive for holding cash. Reserves held for precautionary reasons could be in the form of easily-realized short-term investments which are discussed below:

Speculative motive, companies may build up cash reserves in order to take advantage of any attractive investment opportunities that may arise, for example in the takeover market (Van, 2004). Such reserves are held for speculative reasons. If a company has significant speculative cash reserves for which it cannot see an advantageous use, it may choose to enhance shareholder value by returning them to shareholders, for example by means of a share repurchase scheme or a special cash dividend.

Days Operating Cycle: Days operating cycle measures the efficiency with which the firms manage their inventory and receivables; it is the sum of raw material cycle (in days), work in progress cycle (in days), finished goods cycle (in days) and receivables (conversion period, in days), (Vineet & Sukhdev, 2013). The lower the days operating cycle the better it is and it depicts that the firm is minimizing its investment in working capital and accelerating its working capital ratio. Reduction in operating cycle shall unleash funds which can be alternatively deployed by the firm (Anand, 2001).

Days Working Capital: Days' working capital is the days operating cycle less trade creditors (accounts payables period, in days); it measures the liquidity risk of the firms (Vineet & Sukhdev, 2013). They further lament that, days working capital is a measure of the cash conversion cycle that gives insight about the underlying health of a business. It is a key metric because it measures the average number of days tied up in net working capital in the operating cycle. If day's working capital is trending upwards over time then it will have a negative financial impact on overall company profit.

Moss and Stine, (2003) state that, in order to ensure the business's financial performance, it has been argued that the cash conversion cycle should be reduced to the point where the business's operations are not hurt. Therefore the shorter the cash conversion cycle, the more

efficient the internal operations of the business, (Gentry, 2010). By management streamlining and wringing cash out of the operating or working capital cycle, profitability increases, the need for external financing is reduced, and a cash crunch that may result in illiquidity and eventual bankruptcy is precluded (Chang, 2008, Maness, 2005). Moreover, decreasing the cash conversion cycle improves the cash flow position of the business by providing the business with financial flexibility to adjust to changes in business activity (Moss & Stine, 2008).

2.2.2 Financial Performance

Performance is the function of the ability of an organization to gain and manage the resources in several different ways to develop competitive advantage (Iswatia, 2007). According to Iswaita (2007), revealed that there are two kinds of performance, financial performance and non-financial performance; and financial performance emphasizes on variables related directly to financial report. Iswatia also established that financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time and can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggression (Stewart, 2009).

Company performance is very essential to management as it is an outcome which has been achieved by an individual or a group of individuals in an organization related to its authority and responsibility in achieving the goal legally, not against the law, and conforming to the morale and ethic. Company's performance is evaluated in three dimensions. The first dimension is company's productivity, or processing inputs into outputs efficiently. The second is profitability dimension, or the level of which company's earnings are bigger than

its costs. The third dimension is market premium, or the level of which company's market value is exceeding its book value (Weinraub, 2004).

Performance is a difficult concept, in terms of both definition and measurement. It has been defined as the result of activity, and the appropriate measure selected to assess corporate performance is considered to depend on the type of organization to be evaluated, and the objectives to be achieved through that evaluation. Researchers in the strategic management field have offered a variety of models for analyzing financial performance. However, little consensus has emerged on what constitutes a valid set of performance criteria. For instance, researchers have suggested that studies on financial performance should include multiple criteria analysis. This multidimensional view of performance implies that different models or patterns of relationship between corporate performance and its determinants will emerge to demonstrate the various sets of relationships between dependent and independent variables in the estimated models (Ostroff, 2003).

Return on Assets

This is very important ratio for firms deciding whether or not open a new project. On the basis of this ratio a firm is going to open a project they expect to earn a profit on it, return on asset is the profit they would receive. Generally put, if return on assets is more than what the firm borrows at, then the project should be accepted, if it is not more than that, then it should be rejected. The return on assets is very important and provide a standard for changing how efficiently financial management employs the average amount which is invested in the firm's assets, whether the amount come from investor or creditors. A low level of return on assets shows that the profits are low for the amount of assets. The return on asset ratio calculates how efficiently profits are being collected from the assets employee. A low return on assets

ratio when compared with industry average indicates an inefficient utilization of business assets. Chiu, (2006) and Wu (2001) showed that a firm's return also affects measures of working capital management. First, Wu (2001) showed that the working capital requirement and the performance of the firm have mutual effects, subsequently, Chiu, (2006) found that the return on assets (ROA) has a negative influence on calculate of working capital management. This can be explained in two ways. First, as companies with good performance can get outside capital more easily, they can invest in other large profitable investments (Chiu, 2006).

According to Shin and Soenen (2003), firms with greater returns have good working capital management because of their market dominance, because they have larger bargaining power with supplier and customers. Petersen and Rajan (2005) also showed that companies with higher profitability receive significantly more credit from their suppliers. Thus, the variable return on assets, which is calculated by the ratio earnings before interest and tax over total assets, was introduced into the analysis and it is expected that this factor will have a negative effect on the cash conversion cycle.

Return on Equity (ROE)

It tells what percentage of profit the company makes for every monetary unit of equity invested in the company. ROE doesn't specify how much cash will be returned to the shareholders, since that depends on the company's decision about dividend payments and on how much the stock price appreciates. However, it's a good indication of whether the company is even capable of generating a return that is worth whatever risk the investment may entail (Berman, Case and Knight, 2013). ROE is usually calculated by dividing net profit by average shareholders' equity. As pointed out by Herciu, Ogorean and Belascu (2011),

company profits are not relevant to investors except to the extent to which they relate to other indicators. Afore mentioned authors used ROS, ROA and ROE in order to identify a relation between effect and effort, where effect is profit while effort is given by either sales, total assets, or the stockholder's equity.

The amount of net income is returned as a percentage of shareholder equity. Return on equity calculate a firms profitability by investigating how much profit a firms achieve with the money of shareholder have invested. On the basis of this the return on equity is the most important ratio. Return on equity investigate how much gain a firms earned in comparison to the total amount of shareholder equity that show on the balance sheet. Shareholder equity is foundation of accounting that shows the assets which is produced by the retained earnings of the business and the paid up capital of the owners. Every firm whether it is profit oriented or not is concerned with its main objectives. One of the most usable tools of financial ratio is profitability ratio which is used to determine whether the company is on the bottom line. Profitability ratio calculates the important to firm's manager and owners alike. If a small business has outside investors who have put their own money into the firm, the first owner has to indicate the profitability to those equity investors. Return on equity calculates as the ratio of net profit after taxes to stockholder equity. The expected return to the aggregate stock market is a very important component in the decision of both single investor and corporate investor, as emphasized by Merton (2007).

Merton (2007) stated that net income is used for a fiscal year after taxes and preferred stock dividend but previous common stock dividend. He also stated that shareholder equity does not include preferred stock because it is used as an annual. Return on equity different across different industries. So that why it is used to compare return on equity with the firm's

previous values or return on equity of similar firms (Alexei, 2011). Some industries have large return on equity and some have low return on equity it is depend on the nature of firms either a large industry or small. Alexei (2011) indicates that the firms with a large return on equity ratio have better investment than small firms. In general, the firms which are less capital intensive and with a small return on equity have very low competition but the firms which are large return on equity and having very tough competition with each other because their return on equity is very large (Alexei, 2011).

2.2.3 Relationship between working capital management and financial performance

Theoretically the level of investment in current assets has a bearing on the performance of the firm. Excess investment in working capital casts a negative impact on the profitability of a firm and positive impact on the liquidity. Studies on the association of level of investment in current assets and the performance have always claimed inverse relationship on the degree of association both at micro and macro levels. Working capital management involves managing the relationship between a firm's short-term assets and its short-term liabilities. The goal of working capital management is to ensure that the firm is able to continue its operations and that it has sufficient cash flow to satisfy both maturing short-term debt and upcoming operational expenses. A company can be endowed with assets and profitability but short of liquidity if its assets cannot readily be converted into cash (Githinji, 2015).

Positive working capital is required to ensure that a firm is able to continue its operations and that it has sufficient funds to satisfy both maturing short-term debt and upcoming operational expenses (Afza & Nazir, 2019). Working capital management is considered a very important element in analysing an organizations' performance. Working capital management, a managerial accounting strategy, focuses on maintaining efficient levels of components of

working capital, current assets and current liabilities, in respect to each other. Efficient management of working capital ensures a company has sufficient cash flow to meet its short-term debt obligations and operating expenses. While a company's prime objective is to maximize profitability and increase shareholders wealth, there is need to obtain a balance between liquidity and profitability in conducting the day to day operations to ensure its smooth running and meeting obligations of a company (Eljelly, 2014).

To observe how working capital management can affect profitability, one needs to take a look at a company's cash flows. As Shin and Soenen (2018) state in their study, a longer cash conversion cycle might indicate that a company's sales are rising and that the company can compete by having lax credit policies or high inventories. But on the contrary, a higher cash conversion cycle can actually hurt a company's profitability by increasing the time that cash is tied to non-interest bearing accounts such as accounts receivable. By shortening the cash conversion cycle, the company's cash flows will have a higher net present value (NPV) because cash is received quicker.

Arnold (2015) asserts that if there is too little working capital, it results in inventories, finished goods and customers credit not being available in sufficient quantity. On the other hand, if there are excessive levels of working capital, the firm has unnecessary additional cost: the cost of tying up funds plus the storage, ordering and handling costs of being overburdened with stock. This creates a sort of imbalance in the working capital components, making their management difficult which in practice is a situation that firms (both small and fast growing ones, even multinationals) are confronted with. As a result therefore, the ultimate goal of working capital management is to ensure that firms are able to continue their operations with sufficient cash flow that will service their long term debts and satisfy both

maturing short term obligations (debt) and upcoming operational expenses. Hence, organizations should try as much as possible to meet up with this goal so as to avoid being caught up in the trap of ineffective management of working capital components.

2.3 Theoretical Review

This section elucidates the major theories on working capital management and organizational performance. Some of the theories examined in this section include: The modern portfolio theory, operating and cash conversion cycle theory, as well as the resource-based theory.

2.3.1 The Modern Portfolio Theory

Harry Markowitz 1991, an American economist in the 1950s developed a theory of "portfolio choice," which allows investors to analyse risk relative to their expected return. For this work Markowitz, a professor at Baruch College at the City University of New York, shared the 1990 Nobel Memorial Prize in Economic Sciences with William Sharpe and Merton Miller.

Markowitz's theory is today known as the Modern Portfolio Theory, (MPT). The MPT is a theory of investment which attempts to maximize portfolio expected return for a given amount of portfolio risk, or equivalently minimize risk for a given level of expected return, by carefully choosing the proportions of various assets. Although the MPT is widely used in practice in the financial industry, in recent years, the basic assumptions of the MPT have been widely challenged.

The Modern Portfolio Theory, an improvement upon traditional investment models, is an important advance in the mathematical modelling of finance. The theory encourages asset diversification to hedge against market risk as well as risk that is unique to a specific

company. The theory (MPT) is a sophisticated investment decision approach that aids an investor to classify, estimate, and control both the kind and the amount of expected risk and return; also called Portfolio Management Theory. Essential to the portfolio theory are its quantification of the relationship between risk and return and the assumption that investors must be compensated for assuming risk. Portfolio theory departs from traditional security analysis in shifting emphasis from analysing the characteristics of individual investments to determining the statistical relationships among the individual securities that comprise the overall portfolio (Edwin & Martins, 1997).

The MPT mathematically formulates the concept of diversification in investing, with the aim of selecting a collection of investment assets that has collectively lower risk than any individual asset (Edwin & Martins, 1997). The possibility of this can be seen intuitively because different types of assets often change in value in opposite ways. But diversification lowers risk even if assets' returns are not negatively correlated-indeed, even if they are positively correlated (Edwin & Martins, 1997). More technically, the MPT models an asset return as a normally distributed function (or more generally as an elliptically distributed random variable), define risk as the standard deviation of return, and models a portfolio as a weighted combination of assets so that the return of a portfolio is the weighted combination of the assets' returns (Edwin & Martins, 1997). By combining different assets whose returns are not perfectly positively correlated, MPT seeks to reduce the total variance of the portfolio return (Edwin & Martins, 1997). MPT also assumes that investors are rational and markets are efficient. The fundamental concept behind the MPT is that assets in an investment portfolio should not be selected individually, each on their own merits. Rather, it is important

to consider how each asset changes in price relative to how every other asset in the portfolio changes in price (Markowitz, 1991).

Generally, assets with higher expected returns are riskier (Taleb, 2007). For a given amount of risk, the MPT describes how to select a portfolio with the highest possible expected return. Or, for a given expected return, the MPT explains how to select a portfolio with the lowest possible risk (the targeted expected return cannot be more than the highest returning available security, of course, unless negative holdings of assets are possible). The MPT assumes that investors are risk averse, meaning that given two portfolios that offer the same expected return, investors will prefer the less risky one. Thus, an investor will take on increased risk only if compensated by higher expected returns. Conversely, an investor who wants higher expected returns must accept more risk and the exact trade-off will be the same for all investors, but different investors will evaluate the trade-off differently based on individual risk aversion characteristics (Taleb, 2007). The implication is that a rational investor will not invest in a portfolio if a second portfolio exists with a more favourable risk expected return profile that is, if for that level of risk an alternative portfolio exists which has better expected returns (Taleb, 2007). The MPT is therefore a form of diversification. Under certain assumptions and for specific quantitative definitions of risk and return, MPT explains how to find the best possible diversification strategy.

Despite its theoretical relevance, the MPT has been highly criticized; its simplistic assumptions being a predominant bias. Critics question its viability as an investment strategy, because its model of financial markets does not match the real world in many ways. In recent years, basic underlying assumptions of the MPT have been grossly challenged by fields such as the behavioral economics (Taleb, 2007). Efforts to translate the theoretical foundation of

the theory into a viable portfolio construction algorithm have been plagued by technical difficulties stemming from the instability of the original optimization problem with respect to available data. Recent research shows that instabilities of this type disappear when a regularizing constraint or penalty term is incorporated in the optimization procedure.

2.3.2 Cash Conversion Cycle Theory

The cash conversion cycle theory approach was developed by Richards and Laughlin (1980). In their work, Richards and Laughlin saw the need to have a critical look at working capital management and its individual components. They felt, that, although a substantial portion of financial manager`s time is spent on decision relating short-term assets and liabilities, little attention has been given by most of the literature and researchers in this direction. Accordingly, they describe the receivables, inventories and payables as the constituents of the cash conversion cycle model.

The theory of the cash conversion cycle centres on explaining a cycle that begins from the payment for the purchase of raw materials, through to its transformation and the emergence of new product, to the collection of receivables from the buyers and possible debtors of the interaction as a result of the stock sale. Undoubtedly, financial managers and all related financial analysts appreciate at least at an intuitive level that all working capital investments do not have the same life expectancy, and their transformation rate to usable flows of liquidity is always not at the same speed (Richard & Laughlin, 2008).

While the analysis of an individual firm`s CCC is helpful, industry benchmarks are crucial for a company to evaluate its CCC performance and assess opportunities for improvements because the length of CCC may differ from industry to industry. Therefore the correct way is

to compare a specific firm to the industry in which it operates (Hutchinson, 2007). The cash conversion cycle is used as a comprehensive measure of working capital as it shows the time lag between expenditure for the purchase of raw materials and the collection of sales of finished goods (Padachi, 2006). Day-to-day management of a firm's short term assets and liabilities plays an important role in the success of the firm. Firms with growing long term prospects and healthy bottom lines do not remain solvent without good liquidity management (Jose & Lancaster, 1996). By approximating these three periods with the financial ratios of inventory days, trade receivables days and trade payables days, the length of the cash conversion cycle (CCC). Cash conversion cycle is measured by adding inventory days and trade receivable days and subtracting trade payable days.

The firm's on going liquidity is a function of its cash conversion cycle, hence the appropriateness of evaluation by cash conversion cycle ,rather than liquidity measures. According to Arnold (2008) the shorter the CCC, the fewer are the resources needed by the company. So the longer the cycle the higher will be the investment in the working capital. But also a longer cycle could increase sales, which could lead to higher profitability. But this longer cycle, will also lead to higher investment and could rise faster than the benefits of the higher profitability. They also argued that a longer cash conversion cycle might indicate that a company's sales are rising and that the company can compete by having lax credit policies or high inventories. But on the contrary, a higher CCC can actually hurt a company's profitability by increasing the time that cash is tied to non-interest bearing accounts such as accounts receivables. By shortening the CCC the company's cash flows will have a higher net present value because cash is received quicker. The number of days accounts receivables;

inventories and accounts payables are used as the operationalization of the management of trade credit and inventory (Sharma and Kumar, 2011).

Therefore, in the overall, one can conveniently say that the cash conversion cycle theory is the most central one in explaining working capital management as it is concerned with all the concepts and components, ranging from raw materials to finished products, and outputs representing inventory levels, to receivables and payment representing the cash aspect.

2.3.3 Resource Based Theory

Resources are the basis of business survival and corporate profitability. The resources could either be human or material. When taking stock of a firm's resources, a distinction needs to be made between resources and capabilities. Resources are inputs into the production process they are considered as the fundamental unit of analysis. The resources of a firm include items such as capital equipment, patents, brand names, the skill associated with individual employees, finance and so on. Independently, fewer resources are productive. Any productive activity must require the coordination and cooperation of teams of resources, while a capability is viewed as the ability or capacity of a team of resources to perform certain activity or task. Therefore, by implication resources are the sources of a given firm's capability (Grant, 2001).

The Link: Resource-based theory is used in this context to include the cognitive ability of individual managers of businesses as to ensure effective management of the short-term asset of the business (working capital) (Alvarez & Busenitz, 2001). This therefore connotes that managers have individual-specific resources that facilitates and ensures the recognition of new opportunities, effective assembling of resources, as well as the psyche of making

payments, and recovering of receivables as and when due to ensure effective management of working capital and ultimately the firm's profitability.

This study is anchored on two theories, the resource based theory and cash conversion cycle theory. The resource based theory centred on the dependent variable which is organizational performance, while cash conversion cycle (CCC) theory explains the independent variable, which is working capital management. The CCC is a very important component of working capital management and financial management because it directly affects the liquidity and profitability of the company. It deals with current assets and current liabilities which constituted the independent variables in this study.

2.5 Empirical Review

This section examines past and current empirical findings of various researchers on studies that are functional, technical, and beneficial to this research. It highlights past studies on working capital management on financial performance, and other related topics.

Dada et al (2021) assessed the impact of working capital management on corporate financial performance of consumer goods sector in Nigeria. The study specifically determined the impact of average collection period on the return on assets of consumer goods industries in Nigeria; assessed the effect of cash conversion cycle on the return on assets of consumer goods industries in Nigeria and evaluated the effect of average payment period on the return on assets of consumer goods industries in Nigeria. Panel data spanning five years (2013-2017) was gathered for five consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Panel estimation techniques such as descriptive, correlation, fixed effect (cross section and time specific), random effect and other post estimation tests were used in the study. Findings from the study indicated that

average collection period exerts negative insignificant impact on the profitability of consumer goods firms with coefficient estimate of $-.0000662$ ($p=0.848>0.05$); cash conversion cycle exerts negative insignificant impact on profitability of consumer goods firms with coefficient estimate of $-.0002468$ ($p=0.527>0.05$) and average payment period exerts negative significant impact on the profitability of consumer goods firms in Nigeria with coefficient estimate of $.0016386$ ($p=0.049<0.05$). Premise on these findings, the study suggested that management of manufacturing firms should adopt effective cost reduction strategies, measures to control labour cost vis-à-vis ensuring adequate supervision of workers, monitor firm's assets and occasion employee training.

Ikpefane et al, (2021) examined the management of working capital in deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. This study evaluated the impact of liquidity on banks' performance to analyse how their competitiveness influences capital adequacy and assessed the correlation between loans and advances and deposit money banks' profitability. The study utilized a regression analysis, in which panel data was used based on data retrieved from the banks' financial statements from 2010 to 2017. The findings showed that the primary reason banks hold highly liquid assets is to guard against a rise in demand or unforeseen circumstances. Another reason is to finance working capital operations based on the theory of liquid assets. Therefore, based on the findings it is recommended that direct policies are implemented to ensure that high-volume cash transactions are dramatically reduced.

Almomani, Almomani and Obeidat (2021) investigated the moderating effect of working capital investment and financing policy on the relationship between working capital management efficiency and the financial performance of industrial firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE). To achieve the objective of the study, this study used time

series and data covering the period 2010–2018. A sample of 42 manufacturing firms listed on the ASE was used in the analysis and hypotheses testing. Return on assets is used to measure financial performance, while inventory turnover, receivables turnover, current assets turnover, working capital turnover, and inventory-to-sales ratio are used to measure the working capital management efficiency. This study involved two hypotheses, and both hypotheses were tested to emphasize a 95 percent level of confidence. For data analysis, we used descriptive statistics and the multiple linear regression method was used for hypotheses testing. The study found that inventory turnover, receivables turnover, current assets turnover, and working capital turnover affect the financial performance of the manufacturing firms, whereas no substantial differences were found between the direct or the moderating models in estimating financial performance. The study recommended that manufacturing industry should give more consideration to working capital management to enhance their financial performance.

Olayemi (2021) explored the relationship between working capital management and performance of selected firms quoted on Nigeria stock exchange. This work focused on healthcare and consumer goods sector which has not been adequately researched on by past literatures. Ten companies from the health and food and beverages sectors listed on NSE were selected. Secondary data were used and obtained from the annual financial reports of the selected companies from 2012– 2019. Panel data analysis and Hausmann tests were used to examine the effect of working capital management on firm performance. Findings revealed that average collection period has positive significant effects on firm performance while firm size has negative but significant effect on firm performance. The study concluded that firms would be adversely affected if it takes them longer period to retrieve payments due from their

customers. This study used a few of the determinants of performance. There are other determinants of performance that can be used by other studies. This study shed more light on the issue of working capital and firm performance, especially on sectors that have not been adequately researched on.

Chinedu (2021) evaluated working capital management on the financial performance of food and beverage companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange is investigated in this study. The study used an ex-post-facto research design. From a population of twelve (12) food and beverage firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, a sample of nine (9) was chosen. The data for the study came from the sampled companies' annual reports and accounts, and the hypotheses were tested using regression analysis in E-View 9.0. Inventory has a negative influence on enterprises' return on assets, according to the study, however this effect is not statistically significant. As a result of the findings of this study, the researcher recommended that the management of these companies in Nigeria should exhibit carefulness in handling of stock/investors at least to ensure that their stock level will not be below the minimum stock level.

Ibrahim, Usaini and Elijah (2021) examined the effect of working capital management (WCM) on the financial performance of quoted conglomerate firms in Nigeria for the period 2006 to 2016. Account receivable period (ARP), account payable period (APP), inventory turnover period (INV) and cash conversion cycle (CCC) were adopted as the proxies for WCM while return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA) and return on investments (ROI) were adopted as proxies for financial performance. Secondary data were obtained from ten (10) quoted conglomerate firms' financial statements and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used for the analysis. The study reveals that APP and CCC have positive effect

on financial performance; while ARP and INV have negative effect on financial performance. The general result indicates that there is significant effect of WCM on financial performance (ROA, ROE and ROI) of quoted conglomerate firms in Nigeria. It was recommended that the companies should; ensure speedy collections of account receivables; increase account payable period; formulate and implement effective strategies for inventory management system that minimizes inventory turnover period and management should ensure that investments in working capital is optimized by reducing the length of time from the actual outlay of cash for purchases until the collection of receivables resulting from the sales of goods or services.

Umar and AbdulQadir (2021) studied the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of nonfinancial companies quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange over the period 2014 – 2018 while using a panel research design. This work is unique because it considers a sample of 71 companies drawn from all the 10 non-financial sectors of the NSE. Unlike most extant studies, financial performance was captured by earnings per share as a proxy, while the right-hand side variable being working capital management was denominated by Accounts receivable period, Inventory turnover period, and Accounts payable period. This study also considered the effect of some control variables namely annual capital expenditure, age of firm, GDP, firm size, growth of the company, and firm leverage on EPS. Data were retrieved from the Nigerian Stock Exchange 2019 Factbook. The model estimation technique adopted was the Pooled Ordinary Least Squares, fixed effect, and random effect methods. Results from this study are consistent with the theoretical position that all aspects of working capital management have a significant effect on financial performance. While ITP and ACP were negatively related to EPS, APP was found to have a

positive relationship with EPS. The research results also reveal that although all the control variables were found to be significant, only the age of the firm was deemed to be positively related to EPS. Based on the findings, the research recommended that firms should focus their managerial attention on lowering their ITP and ACP while increasing their APP, as results indicate that management of these elements of working capital can translate into liquidity and higher profitability.

Abdul-Khadir, Abul and Aiyu (2020) examined the effect of working capital management (WCM) on the financial performance of quoted conglomerate firms in Nigeria for the period 2006 to 2016. Account receivable period (ARP), account payable period (APP), inventory turnover period (INV) and cash conversion cycle (CCC) were adopted as the proxies for WCM while return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA) and return on investments (ROI) were adopted as proxies for financial performance. Secondary data were obtained from ten (10) quoted conglomerate firms' financial statements and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used for the analysis. The study reveals that APP and CCC have positive effect on financial performance; while ARP and INV have negative effect on financial performance. The general result indicates that there is significant effect of WCM on financial performance (ROA, ROE and ROI) of quoted conglomerate firms in Nigeria. It was recommended that the companies should; ensure speedy collections of account receivables; increase account payable period; formulate and implement effective strategies for inventory management system that minimizes inventory turnover period and management should ensure that investments in working capital is optimized by reducing the length of time from the actual outlay of cash for purchases until the collection of receivables resulting from the sales of goods or services.

Kimutai and Muigai (2018) examined the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nairobi County, Kenya. This study looked at the effect of management of all the components of working capital management namely; cash management, accounts payable management, accounts receivable management and inventory management on profitability of Small and Medium Enterprises. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The study population comprised of SMEs in Nairobi County which fall within the Top 100 SMEs in Kenya. A sample size of 28 SMEs which represented 30% of the target population was selected through stratified random sampling in a heterogeneous population. The data collected was analysed through correlation and regression methods using SPSS version 22. The findings revealed that that cash management, inventory management, accounts payable management and accounts receivable management are all significant determinants of financial performance of SMEs in Nairobi County and demonstrated knowledge of working capital management in the Top 100 SMEs in Nairobi County which contributed to the outstanding outcome in the level of financial performance. The findings also indicated that the most important variable in the model was accounts payable management ($\beta = 0.457$). This was followed by cash management ($\beta = 0.235$), accounts receivable management ($\beta = 0.182$) and inventory management ($\beta = 0.179$) in that order. The study, therefore, recommended that Small and Medium Enterprises need to have a cash balance policy, inventory management policy, accounts payable management policy and accounts receivable policy because the policies impact positively on the overall financial performance.

Osuma, Ailemen, Osabohien and Eriki (2017) investigated the relationship between working capital management and profitability of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. The

specific objective of this study was to examine how the profitability of firms will be enhanced through the effective management of working capital while, the general objective is to examine profitability and the working capital position of some selected banks in Nigeria. To empirically carry out the analysis, a pooled ordinary least squares (OLS) was engaged for the selected variables such as net interest income, current ratio, profit after tax, monetary policy rate, return on equity and return on asset for the period of seven years (2010 to 2016). It was found that working capital management has a significant negative impact on the performance of the selected banks and therefore recommended for a periodic review of the minimum capital base of the banking sector in other to cushion the effects of inflation and inculcate the time value of money.

2.5 Gap in Literature

Based on the empirical works reviewed, a significant gap in the literature emerges concerning the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Specifically, previous studies have various limitations, such as focusing on different sectors, time periods, or specific components of working capital management, rather than offering a comprehensive and recent analysis. There exist a sectorial gap Dada et al. (2021) focused on the consumer goods sector from 2013 to 2017, Olayemi (2021) examined healthcare and consumer goods sectors from 2012 to 2019. Chinedu (2021) focused on food and beverage companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

There is also a gap of components of Working Capital. Dada et al. (2021) analyzed average collection period, cash conversion cycle, and average payment period. Ibrahim, Usaini, and Elijah (2021) examined account receivable period, account payable period, inventory

turnover period, and cash conversion cycle. Umar and AbdulQadir (2021) considered accounts receivable period, inventory turnover period, and accounts payable period.

Another gap is that of time period, studies cover varying periods, such as 2010-2016 (Osuma et al., 2017), 2013-2017 (Dada et al., 2021), and 2014-2018 (Umar and AbdulQadir, 2021), none focusing on the most recent years up to 2023.

There is also a gap of geographical focus, Almomani et al. (2021) investigated firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. Kimutai and Muigai (2018) focused on SMEs in Nairobi County, Kenya.

To address the identified gaps, this study examined a comprehensive Analysis of Manufacturing Sector with specific focuses on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria, incorporating various sub-sectors to ensure a holistic understanding of the industry. Also to extend the study period to cover data from 2014 to 2023 to provide more recent insights and trends. The study also utilized multiple measures of financial performance such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) to provide a comprehensive analysis. By addressing these gaps this study will fill the existing gaps and contribute to a more to understanding of the relationship between working capital management and financial performance in Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with the research design, population of the study, sample size, sources of data, method of data analysis model of specification and limitations of the methodology.

3.2 Research Design

This study adopts ex-post facto research design. Ex-post facto research design involves the ascertaining of the impact of past factors on the present happening or event. The research design is also adopted due to the fact that, the audited financial statements of listed manufacturing companies which are the main source of data are already in existence.

3.2.1 Population of the study

The population of this study consists of all the manufacturing goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group and have complete financial records on their websites or Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) for the period of 2013 – 2023. As at 31st December 2023 Manufacturing Goods Companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group were forty-four (44). The manufacturing companies are made up of three sectors, namely; consumer goods companies (21 companies), oil and gas companies (10 companies) and industrial goods companies (12 companies). The list of the companies is given in appendix I

3.2.2 Sample size

This study adopts filter sampling technique. However, the desired sample will be determined based on established criteria as follows:

- i. The company must be listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) a year before the beginning year of the study (2013).
- ii. The company must have been trading constantly at the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group.
- iii. The company must have its annual report accessible for the relevant years of this study.

After considering the above criteria fifteen (15) companies were sampled for the study.

3.3 Sources of Data

This study used secondary sources of data. The data was obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the listed manufacturing companies listed on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) for the period 2013 to 2023. This documentary source of data were used because of the nature of variables under study.

3.4 Definition of Variables

This study is aimed at examining the effect of working capital management on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. As a result, the dependent variable is financial performance which is defined as the measure of how healthy a company is operating in terms of profitability. It is measured in terms of Return on Assets (ROA). The Independent variable for the study is working capital management which is the ability of the companies to be able to meet up with its matured obligation. It is the difference between current assets and current liabilities. Four dimensions of working capital management are

examined: Average Collection Period (ACP), Average Payment Period (APP) Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC).

3.4.1 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable for this study is financial performance proxied by Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE)

Return on Assets (ROA): It determines a company's ability to make use of its assets. It is measured as the ratio of Profit After Tax (PAT) divide by Total Assets (TA) $ROA = \frac{PAT}{TA}$

Return on Equity (ROE): It is used to determine the ability of a company to be able to make return on its investment in Equity. It is measured as $ROE = \frac{PAT}{TE}$

3.4.2 Independent Variables

The independent variable for this study is working capital management which is proxied by; Average Collection Period (ACP), Average Payment Period (APP), Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC).

Average Collection Period (ACP): The Average Collection Period (ACP) is a financial metric that measures the average number of days it takes for a company to collect payments from its customers for credit sales. It is also known as the Days Sales Outstanding (DSO) ratio. A lower ACP indicates that a company collects payments from its customers more quickly, which is generally favourable as it improves cash flow and liquidity.

Average Payment Period (APP): The Average Payment Period (APP) is a financial metric that measures the average number of days it takes a company to pay its suppliers or creditors.

It assesses how efficiently a company manages its accounts payable by determining the average time it takes to settle outstanding invoices or bills. A lower APP indicates that a company pays its suppliers more quickly, which can positively impact relationships with suppliers and may provide opportunities for discounts or favourable credit terms.

Inventory Turnover Period (ITP): The Inventory Turnover Period (ITP), also known as Days Inventory Outstanding (DIO), is a financial metric that measures the average number of days it takes for a company to sell its entire inventory. It assesses how efficiently a company manages its inventory by determining the average time it takes to convert inventory into sales. A lower ITP indicates that a company sells its inventory more quickly, which is generally favourable as it reduces holding costs and improves cash flow.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC): The Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) is a financial metric that measures the time it takes for a company to convert its investments in inventory and other resources into cash flows from sales. It evaluates the efficiency of a company's working capital management by assessing how long it takes to generate cash from its operating activities. A shorter CCC indicates that a company efficiently manages its working capital, while a longer CCC suggests inefficiencies in cash flow management.

The Variables used in this study are presented in a Table 3 below:

Table 3: Measurement of Variables

Variable	Measurement
Dependent Variable	
Return on Assets (ROA)	$\frac{PAT}{TA} \times 100$
Return on Equity (ROE)	$\frac{PAT}{TE} \times 100$
Independent Variable	
1. Average Collection Period (ACP)	$ACP = \frac{\text{Average Trade Debtors}}{\text{Turnover}} \times 365$ days
2. Average Payment Period (APP)	$APP = \frac{\text{Accounts payable}}{\text{cost of sales}} \times 365$
3. Inventory Turnover Period (ITP)	$ITP = \frac{\text{Average Inventory}}{\text{Cost of Sales}} \times 365$
4. Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)	$CCC = \text{Days of Sale Outstanding} + \text{No. Of Day in Inventories} - \text{Days of Payable Outstanding}$

Source: *Researchers' Compilation; 2024*

3.5 Techniques of Data Analysis

This study will employ linear regression technique of data analysis. Panel regression technique is chosen because of its effectiveness and efficiency in the statistical estimate of the relationship/impact of one variable on another variable. (Using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 20.0) Hence, this is consistent with the objective of this study, which is the effect of working capital management on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Regression will be adopted as a tool for hypotheses tests, owing to the fact that it is an appropriate parametric tool that estimates the impact of one or more variables on another, especially when that data are of parametric nature.

3.6 Model Specification

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ACP}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{APP}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ITP}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{CCC}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

$$\text{ROE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ACP}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{APP}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ITP}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{CCC}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(ii)$$

Where:

ROA = Return on total assets;

ROE = Return on Equity;

ACP = Average Collection Period

APP = Average Payable Period;

ITP = Inventory Turnover Period;

CCC = Cash Conversion Period;

ε = error term

β_0 = Constant

it = Company 1 for time period.

$\beta_1, 2, 3 \dots 4$ = Parameters to be estimated

Decision Rule

The study establishes the following criteria for the acceptance and rejection of the null hypotheses. Reject the null hypothesis if the P value of the

correlation result is less than 0.05 otherwise accept the Null hypothesis. This is summarily put below.

P value < 0.05Reject the null hypotheses

P value > 0.05Accept the null hypotheses

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of working capital management on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This chapter firstly presented descriptive statistics analysis. Furthermore, the chapter presented and discussed the results of the correlation and regression analysis, followed by testing of hypotheses and finally discussion of findings. The statistical package for social science (SPSS), version 20 will aid the analysis of data.

4.2 Data Presentation and Analysis

This section of the chapter presents data extracted from the annual accounts of listed manufacturing companies (see data in appendix I) for a period of 10 years (i.e. 2014 - 2023). Data in respect to the study independent variables were regressed with two common dependent variables (Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE)) and the results are presented in the subsequent sections

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

This sub-section presents the result of descriptive statistics for the dependent variable Financial Performance proxies by (Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) and independent variables; Average Collection Period (ACP), Average Payment Period (APP), Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC). As indicated by N in the result table, the number of observation for the study is 15 manufacturing companies studied for 10 years therefore, $15 \times 10 = 150$. The table further shows that all the series display a high level of consistency as their mean and standard deviation values are

perpetually within the maximum and minimum values of these series. Besides, the standard deviation revealed that actual data in the series are not really different from their mean value.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
ROA	220	-1.00	3.63	.0846	.36644
ROE	220	-2.42	4.34	.2339	.59556
ACP	220	.00	77340.22	764.7430	5651.72581
APP	220	.00	3939.02	217.6438	448.66731
ITP	220	.00	631.67	87.8927	85.02435
CCC	220	-988.78	73401.20	634.9960	5290.25288
Valid N (listwise)	220				

Source: Researchs' Computation Using SPSS Version, 20

Data on table 4 shows Return on Assets has a positive value of 0.0846. This implies that most of quoted manufacturing companies have a positive return on assets (ROA) with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.36644. This is means that the ROA of the sampled companies deviate from both sides of the mean at 42.6%, which means that the data is not highly dispersed from its mean. The ROA also has a minimum and maximum value of -1.00 and 3.63 respectively.

More so, that a positive return on equity (ROE) value of 0.2339. This is an indication that most of quoted manufacturing companies have a positive return on equity with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.59556. This is an indication that the ROE of the sampled companies deviate from both sides of the mean at 59.6%, which means that the data is not highly dispersed from its mean. The ROE also has a minimum and maximum value of -2.42 and 4.34 respectively.

Similarly, Average Collection Period (ACP) shows a positive mean value of 764.74 at a deviation of 5651.73. The minimum and maximum values of ACP are 0.00 and 77340.22 respectively.

In the same vein, the mean of Average Payment Period (APP) stood at 217.6438 with a SD of 448.66731. This means that the APP deviates from both sides of the average by 448.66731, meaning that the data is widely dispersed from the mean. The APP also has a minimum of 0.00 and maximum of 3939.02 respectively.

Table 4 also shows that the mean ITP of the sampled companies during the study period was 87.89, with a SD of 85.02. This indicates that the ITP deviates from both sides of the mean by 87.89, meaning that the data is widely dispersed from the mean. The ITP also has a minimum and maximum value of 0.00 and 631.67 respectively.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) shows a mean value of 634.99 and a standard deviation of 5290.25. This means there is a high deviation from cash conversion cycle of the companies during the period of study. The minimum and maximum values are -988.78 and 73401.20 respectively.

4.2.2 Validity Test

This section focuses on the presentation of data validity test to ensure compliance with regression assumptions. The tests carried out include; multi-collinearity test, normality test, autocorrelation.

4.2.2.1 Multi-collinearity check

In an attempt to ensure that the results of this study are robust and valid for interpretation, several diagnostic tests such as variance inflation factor (VIF), Tolerance statistics, is computed and presented in table 5.

Table 4 Collinearity Statistics

	Tolerance	VIF
ACP	.744	1.344
APP	.868	1.152
ITP	.691	1.448
CCC	.802	1.246

Source: SPSS Output

Test for Multicollinearity: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) statistics, tolerance statistics and correlation matrix are used to test for the presence of Multicollinearity among the variables in the model. In respect to Multicollinearity test using VIF, Table 4 above presents results of the variance inflation factor (VIF). Although, there is no formal VIF value for determining presence of multicollinearity, values of VIF that exceed 10 are often regarded as indicating multicollinearity, but in weaker models, values above 2.5 may be a cause for concern (Kouisoyiannis, 1977; Gujarati & Sangeetha, 2007).

Bearing these criteria in mind, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) statistics for all the independent variables of this study consistently fell below 5 (see table 4). This indicates the absence of multicollinearity among the variables. This implies that the model exhibit low risk of potential multicollinearity problems as all the independent variables have a variance inflation factor (VIF) below 10. Also, the tolerance values continuously lies between 1.344 and 0.448 (see table 4). This is more than 0.1; this further substantiates the absence of multicollinearity problems among the independent variables. It is been suggested that tolerance value less than 0.1 almost or certainly indicates a serious collinearity problem (Menard, 1995).

Table 6: Correlation Test for Multicollinearity

		ROA	ROE	ACP	APP	ITP	CCC
ROA	Pearson Correlation	1	.173*	.189**	-.024	-.032	.204**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010	.005	.728	.633	.002
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
ROE	Pearson Correlation	.173*	1	.424**	.335**	-.047	.423**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010		.000	.000	.487	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
ACP	Pearson Correlation	.189**	.424**	1	.800**	-.119	.999**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.000		.000	.078	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
APP	Pearson Correlation	-.024	.335**	.800**	1	-.120	.768**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.728	.000	.000		.076	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
ITP	Pearson Correlation	-.032	-.047	-.119	-.120	1	-.101
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.633	.487	.078	.076		.135
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
CCC	Pearson Correlation	.204**	.423**	.999**	.768**	-.101	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.000	.000	.000	.135	
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Researcher's Computation Using SPSS, Version 20.1

Table 6 shows the Pearson Product movement correlation for all the variables. Correlations result as presented here is further use as check for data validity. These types of checks are necessary because high correlation causes problems about the relative contribution of each predictor to the success of the model (Gujariti, 2007). The correlation matrix presented in table 6 shows the absence of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables as all the variables lies far below the 0.80 which is considered harmful for the purpose of analysis (see Gujarati & Sangeeta, 2007, Berenson & Levine, 1999).

4.2.3 Regression Results

Regression analysis shows how one variable relates with another. It is the main tool used for data analysis in this study. The result of the regression is hereby presented in table 7 for subsequent analysis.

Table 7: Model Summary^b for Return on Assets

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.364 ^a	.133	.117	.34440	.133	8.234	4	215	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), CCC, ACP, APP, ITP

Researcher's Computation Using SPSS, Version 20

Model summaries for the dependent and explanatory variables are shown in Table 7. The table shows R value of 36.4% which indicates a weak relationship between the explanatory variables and Return on Assets (ROA) of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The calculated value of the R² coefficient of determination is 0.133. This shows that the explanatory variables; Average Collection Period (ACP), Average Payment Period (APP), Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) can account for 13.3% of the variation in ROA. In other words, these indicators account for 13.3% of the variation in ROA of Nigerian listed manufacturing companies.

In order to assess the projected shrinkage in R Square that would not generalize to the population, the adjusted R Square value, which is the study's indicator of generalizability, is adjusted for the number of variables included in the regression equation. Our regression equation may be over-fitted to the sample and have limited generalizability, if the adjusted R Square value is significantly lower than the adjusted R Square value. R Square = 0.133 or

13.3% for this study, whereas the adjusted R Square =0.177 or 17.7%. Based on this metric, there is little shrinkage because these values are close (Gujarati & Sangeetha, 2007). The result further indicates that if the entire population is used, the result will deviate from it by 4.4% (i.e. 13.3 – 17.7).

The anticipated value of the F-statistic is 8.234. This shows that the predictor variable as a whole contributed to the variation in the dependent variable and that the association between Return on Assets and the collection of predictor variables (CCC, APP, ITP and ACP) is statistically significant at .000. This shows that the total equation has a significance level of 0.0%, which is lower than the 5% usually accepted level of significance.

Table 8: Model Summary^b for Return on Equity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.340 ^a	.116	.099	.56517	.116	7.047	4	215	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), CCC, ACP, APP, ITP

Researcher’s Computation Using SPSS, Version 20

Table 8 presents model summary for both the dependent and explanatory variables. The R value of 0.340 (34.0%) above indicates the existence of a weak relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is estimated at 0.116. This suggests that 11.6% of the variation in ROE can be explained by the explanatory variable Average Collection Period (ACP), Average Payment Period (APP), Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC). In other words, these predictors contribute 11.6% to the change in ROE of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The adjusted R Square value which is the study's indicator of generalizability is adjusted for the number of variables included in the regression equation is used to estimate the expected shrinkage in R Square that would not generalize to the population (Gujarati & Sangeetha, 2007). If the adjusted R Square value is much lower than the adjusted R Square value, it is an indication that our regression equation may be over-fitted to the sample, and of limited generalizability. For this study, R Square = 0.116 or 11.6% and the Adjusted R Square = 0.099 or 9.9%. These values are close, thus there is minimal shrinkage based on this indicator (Gujarati & Sangeetha, 2007). The result further indicates that if the entire population is used, the result will deviate from it by 1.7% (i.e. 11.6 – 9.9).

Lastly, the F-statistics is estimated at 7.047. This indicates that the predictor variables was as a whole contributing to the variation in the dependent variable and that there exist a statistically significant relationship at 0.000 between Return on Equity and the set of predictor variables (CCC, APP, ITP and ACP). This indicates that the overall equation is significant at 0.000% which is below the 5% generally acceptable level of significance.

Table 9: Model Coefficients^a for Return on Assets

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.653	.106		6.177	.000		
1 ACP	-.073	.041	-.133	-1.803	.073	.744	1.344
APP	-.201	.045	-.304	-4.456	.000	.868	1.152
ITP	-.022	.045	-.037	-.488	.626	.691	1.448
CCC	-.018	.030	-.044	-.619	.537	.802	1.246

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

Researchers' Computation Using SPSS, Version 20

Table 9 presents the model coefficients for all variables used in the study. The coefficient of determination R^2 shows 0.653 indicating that the overall model explained 65.3 percent of the total variations in the dependent variable. Thus shows that these variables (CCC, APP, ITP and ACP) can only explain 65.3 percent of change in company's return on equity leaving 34.7 percent unexplained. This is to say that there are other determinants of company's financial performance other than liquidity management.

However, the result of the estimated model shows for all the variables Average Collection Period (ACP), Average Payment Period (APP), Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) exhibit a negative on Return on Assets (ROA) of listed manufacturing companies in Nigerian with beta coefficients of -0.133, -0.304, -0.037 and -0.044 respectively. This implies that a unit change in all the variables will lead to a decrease increase in ROA at 13.3%, 30.4%, 3.7% and 4.4% respectively thus indicating a negative impact.

Table 10: Coefficients^a for Return on Equity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.170	.173		.979	.329		
1 ACP	-.134	.067	-.150	-2.011	.046	.744	1.344
APP	.284	.074	.264	3.842	.000	.868	1.152
ITP	-.186	.075	-.192	-2.491	.013	.691	1.448
CCC	.035	.049	.051	.717	.474	.802	1.246

a. Dependent Variable: ROE

Researchers' Computation Using SPSS, Version 20

The model coefficients for each of the study's variables are shown in Table 10. The dependent variables of the entire variation was explained by the overall model to the tune of 0.001, as indicated by the coefficient of determination R^2 's value of 0.170%. As a result, it can be seen that four factors (CCC, APP, ITP and ACP) can only account for 0.170% of the change in businesses' return on equity, leaving 83.0% unaccounted for. This means that factors other than dividend policy also affect a company's financial performance.

However, the estimated model's outcome reveals that Average Collection Period (ACP) and Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) have a corresponding standardize coefficient of -0.150 and -0.192 which implies that a unit change in ACP and ITP will lead to 15% and 19.2% decrease in ROE of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Average Payment Period (APP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) have corresponding beta values of 0.264 and 0.051 have a favourable (positive) impact on ROA of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This suggests that a unit change in APP and CCC will lead to increase in ROE of the companies respectively, showing a favourable impact.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

t- test is used to test the significance of the relationship between variables. It is done at 5% level of significance with n-1 degree of freedom. This was done in line with the decision rule earlier stated in chapter three. This test is used to test the following hypotheses:

4.3.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Average Collection Period (ACP) has no significant effect on Financial Performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

In testing the first hypothesis, the results in table 9 and table 10 reveals that Average Collection Period (ACP) had a t-calculated value of -1.803 and -2.011 in respect Return on Assets and return on equity at a correspondent significant probability statistics of 0.073 and 0.046 respectively which lies within the 5% level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The study therefore concludes that Average Collection Period (ACP) has significant effect on Financial Performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

4.3.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Average Payment Period (APP) has no significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

More so, in testing the second hypothesis, the results in table 9 and table 10 reveals that Average Payment Period (APP) had a t-calculated value of -4.456 and 3.842 in respect to Return on Equity and Return on Assets at a correspondent significant probability statistics of 0.000 and 0.000 which lies within 0.05 level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the

null hypothesis. The study therefore concludes that Average Payment Period (APP) has significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

4.3.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) has no significant effect on Financial Performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

In testing the third hypothesis, the results in table 8 and table 9 reveals that Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) had a t-calculated value of -0.488 and -2.491 in respect to return on assets and return equity with a correspondent significant probability statistics of 0.432 and 0.013 which is below 0.05 level of significance. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The study therefore concludes that Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) has significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

4.3.3 Test of Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) has no significant effect on Financial Performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

In testing the third hypothesis, the results in table 8 and table 9 reveals that Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) had a t-calculated value of -0.619 and 0.717 in respect to return on assets and return on equity with a correspondent significant probability statistics of 0.537 and 0.474 which above 0.05 level of significance. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The study therefore concludes that Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) has no significant effect on Financial Performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

This study's main objective was concerned at determining effect of working capital management on Financial Performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria using financial data of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group continuously during the period of 2014 - 2023. Four hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study and tested using t-test statistics. The findings from this test are discussed in the subsequent paragraph.

Average Collection Period and Financial Performance: The first objective of this study sought to investigate whether average collection period has significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Consequently, the null hypotheses were formulated in line with this objective and was tested using 5% level of significance. The dependent variable which was proxied using return on assets and return on equity revealed that average collection period has a significant positive effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Average Collection Period of listed manufacturing companies has a positive beta coefficients. This implies that longer credit periods could be a strategic choice to build and maintain strong customer relationships, which can lead to repeat business, customer loyalty, and increased sales over time. Also offering extended credit terms might give these firms a competitive edge, helping them to capture a larger market share, particularly in a competitive market. In the Nigerian context, longer ACP might be a response to market conditions where customers generally expect longer credit terms due to economic challenges. Firms that adapt to these conditions might achieve better performance. This finding is similar with that of Tsuruta (2019) who in a study of Japanese SMEs found that longer trade credit periods (reflected in ACP) were positively

associated with firm performance. The study suggested that offering trade credit can strengthen customer relationships and sales, outweighing the costs of delayed receivables. Lazaridis and Tryfonidis (2006) in their research on Greek firms found a positive relationship between the cash conversion cycle components (including ACP) and profitability. They argued that strategic management of receivables can lead to better firm performance through enhanced sales and customer loyalty. Also Akoto et al (2013) studying listed manufacturing firms in Ghana, discovered a positive correlation between ACP and firm profitability. They concluded that extending credit to customers could increase sales and, consequently, profitability, especially in markets where credit terms are an essential part of business transactions.

4.4.2 Average Payment Period (APP) and financial performance: The second objective was concerned with examining the effect of average payment period on financial performance (return on assets and return on equity) of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study formulated a null hypothesis in line with this objective and was tested using 5% level of significance for a two tail test. Evidence from the study shows an significant positive effect of average payment period on financial performance. This means that extending the payment period allows firms to hold onto their cash longer, improving their liquidity position. This enables them to utilize available cash for other operational needs or investment opportunities that can enhance profitability. Also by delaying payments to suppliers, firms effectively use their suppliers' credit as an interest-free source of financing. This can free up capital for investment in revenue-generating activities without incurring additional financing costs. Companies with longer APP might have stronger bargaining

power with suppliers, allowing them to negotiate better credit terms without jeopardizing supplier relationships.

This finding is similar with the work done by Deloof (2003) which in a study of Belgian firms found that firms that delayed payments to suppliers significantly improved their profitability. This was attributed to the positive impact on liquidity and the ability to reinvest retained cash. Lazaridis and Tryfonidis (2006) in their research on Greek firms indicated a positive relationship between APP and profitability. Garcia-Teruel and Martinez-Solano (2007) in analysing Spanish SMEs, found that efficient working capital management, including extended payment periods, contributed to higher profitability. This supported the idea that delaying payments helped firms maintain liquidity for operational and investment purposes.

Inventory Turnover Period and financial performance: The third objective of the study was concerned with examining the effect of inventory turnover period on financial performance (return on assets and return on equity) of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study formulated a null hypothesis in line with this objective and was tested using the t-test statistics at 5% level of significance for a two tail test. Evidence from the study shows a significant negative effect of inventory turnover period financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This implies that the company is managing its inventory efficiently, reducing holding costs, and minimizing the risk of obsolescence or spoilage, which can lead to cost savings and higher profitability. Faster inventory turnover results in quicker cash conversion, enhancing liquidity and allowing the firm to reinvest the cash into other profitable ventures or reduce debt, improving ROA and ROE. Also, efficient inventory management ensures that firms can meet customer demand promptly, leading to

higher customer satisfaction and repeat business, which in turn boosts sales and financial performance. This finding is consistent with that of Singh et al. (2017) which in their study on Indian manufacturing firms found a significant negative relationship between ITP and profitability measures like ROA and ROE. Gaur, Fisher, and Raman (2005) in their research on retail firms showed that inventory turnover is positively correlated with financial performance. Vastag and Whybark (2005) in their study on manufacturing firms in the US demonstrated that companies with better inventory management, indicated by shorter ITP, tend to have higher financial performance. The authors linked this to reduced holding costs and better cash flow management.

4.4.4 Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) and Financial Performance: The fourth objective was concerned with examining the effect of cash conversion cycle on financial performance (return on assets and return on equity) of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study formulated a null hypothesis in line with this objective and was tested using the t-test statistics at 5% level of significance for a two tail test. Evidence from the study showed an insignificant positive effect of cash conversion cycle on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Cash Conversion Cycle measures the time it takes for a company to convert its investments in inventory and other resources into cash flows from sales. While theoretically, a shorter CCC should improve liquidity and reduce the need for external financing, which in turn could enhance profitability, the empirical evidence from Nigeria's manufacturing sector indicates otherwise. The findings show that despite managing the CCC efficiently, the expected significant positive impact on financial performance is not consistently observed.

This phenomenon can be attributed to several factors specific to the Nigerian market. For instance, issues such as inefficient inventory management, delays in receivables, and the overall economic environment may dampen the potential benefits of an optimized CCC. Additionally, external factors like supply chain disruptions, regulatory challenges, and inflation can also affect the relationship between CCC and financial performance.

This finding is inconsistent with that of Anser and Malik (2013) found a negative relationship between CCC and profitability in Pakistani firms, suggesting that firms with shorter CCCs tend to perform better financially. Similarly, research on Bangladeshi manufacturing firms highlighted that a reduced CCC could positively influence liquidity and profitability, although this is not universally applicable across all sectors and regions (Chand et al., 2020; Moss and Stine, 1993).

The work of researchers like Deloof (2003) and Nobanee et al. (2011) supports the notion that a shorter CCC is generally associated with better financial performance due to reduced costs related to holding inventory and receivables. However, the Nigerian context, as discussed, reveals that other operational and external factors might overshadow the benefits of a shorter CCC, leading to an insignificant impact on financial performance.

CCC is a crucial component of working capital management and theoretically should enhance financial performance, its actual impact in Nigeria's manufacturing sector appears limited by various external and internal factors. This aligns with the broader literature, indicating that the effectiveness of CCC management can vary significantly across different economic and operational environments (Ebben and Johnson, 2011; Schilling, 1996).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

This study investigates the effect of working capital management on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study adopts the ex-post-facto research design in the investigation. The following are the summary of major findings arrived at through the test of research hypotheses of the study:

1. Average Collection Period (ACP) has significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
2. Average Payment Period (APP) has no significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
3. Inventory Turnover Period (ITP) has no significant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
4. Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) has an insignificant effect on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

Emanating from the results obtained from the data collected and analysed together with hypotheses tests, average cash conversion cycle revealed an insignificant relationship with financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria while average collection period, average payment period, inventory turnover period have no significant relationship with financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations should be taken into considerations.

- i. Companies should develop strategic credit policies that balance the need to extend credit to boost sales with the importance of maintaining healthy cash flows. This includes regular monitoring of receivables and timely collections. They should implement thorough credit assessment procedures to ensure that extended credit is granted to customers with good creditworthiness, minimizing the risk of bad debts. They should offer flexible credit terms based on customer profiles and their payment histories. Tailored credit terms can optimize the benefits of longer ACP while managing risks.
- ii. The companies should negotiate favourable payment terms with suppliers that allow for longer payment periods without harming relationships. This could involve building strong supplier relationships and demonstrating reliable payment history. They should also implement robust cash flow monitoring systems to track the impact of extended payment periods on overall liquidity and ensure that it aligns with the firm's financial strategy. The cash retained from longer payment periods should be strategically utilized for investment in high-return projects, reducing debt, or enhancing operational efficiencies. While extending payment periods can improve liquidity, it is important to maintain good relationships with suppliers. They should ensure that the extended payment terms do not adversely affect the suppliers' financial health or lead to strained relationships.

- iii. Implementing Just-in-Time (JIT) systems can help reduce inventory levels, lower holding costs, and improve turnover rates by synchronizing production schedules with demand. The company should utilize advanced forecasting techniques and data analytics to predict customer demand more accurately, ensuring optimal inventory levels and reducing excess stock. The companies should streamline supply chain processes to reduce lead times and improve coordination with suppliers. This can help maintain lean inventory levels while meeting production requirements. Also they should conduct regular audits to identify slow-moving or obsolete inventory and take corrective actions, such as promotions or discounts, to clear excess stock quickly.
- iv. Manufacturing companies should focus on optimizing the individual components of the cash conversion cycle inventory conversion period, receivables collection period, and payables deferral period. By fine-tuning these components, firms can potentially improve their cash flow and overall financial health. Also, effective inventory management can reduce the inventory conversion period. This includes adopting just-in-time (JIT) inventory systems, improving demand forecasting, and leveraging technology for real-time inventory tracking. They should also implement robust credit management policies to shorten the receivables collection period. This might involve stricter credit terms, offering discounts for early payments, and employing efficient invoicing systems.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

The following are the potential limitations of the study that should be taken into considerations.

- i. This study is limited to only manufacturing companies in Nigeria currently listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. This made it impossible to examine firm characteristics and performance of companies in other sectors of the economy like insurance companies, deposit money banks and other non-banking sectors of the economy. Therefore, it is not possible to generalize the results of this study.
- ii. This study is also limited by the choice of variables used in this study. There are other measures of financial performance aside the ones used in this study.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Studies

Intending researchers in the same area of study can explore the following areas not captured in this study;

1. The effect of working capital management on financial performance of listed manufacturing companies, using variables of financial performance like net profit margin, return on capital employed and net profit margin.
2. This study exclusively concentrated on manufacturing companies in Nigeria; other researchers should consider investigating other industries like, deposit money banks, health sector, agricultural sector etc.

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Company	Year	PAT	TA	SALES	Cost of Sales	Account Payable	TRADE Debtors	IVNT	TE
		N'000	N'000	N'000	N'000	N'000	N'000	N'000	N'000
Cardbury Nigeria Plc	2014	1,153,295	28,811,286	30,518,586	22,134,829	11,742,702	6,093,315	2,392,926	12,749,451
	2015	2,137,319	27,825,194	27,825,194	18,994,967	11,104,368	5,166,194	1,936,455	12,285,297
	2016	-296,403	28,409,000	29,979,410	23,119,007	12,582,771	4,968,703	5,020,938	11,056,733
	2017	299,998	28,423,122	33,079,446	25,644,312	8,860,338	4,890,318	6,252,367	11,742,791
	2018	823,085	27,528,040	35,973,479	28,017,413	10,017,011	3,770,169	5,865,105	12,676,146
	2019	1,070,845	28,801,938	39,326,807	31,001,209	9,617,475	4,529,668	6,062,631	13,566,235
	2020	931,827	33,210,684	35,407,323	29,508,278	10,910,038	3,855,773	5,244,046	13,549,523
	2021	449,712	43,688,291	42,372,034	35,894,401	18,030,034	4,053,339	8,100,730	13,636,354
	2022	583,111	59,713,684	55,212,617	47,489,806	20,484,918	5,164,146	11,913,166	13,302,629
	2023	-19,089,704	63,431,020	80,378,955	63,041,528	25,530,503	7,320,449	11,938,959	-6,513,678
Champion Breweries Plc	2014	-754,523	9,592,381	3,302,383	2,662,451	2,414,360	577,452	354,286	5,870,431
	2015	77,140	10,329,160	3,501,845	2,502,147	3,057,219	677,101	350,133	7,121,637
	2016	530,389	9,961,240	3,864,943	2,797,890	1,281,032	252,177	530,410	7,670,860
	2017	517,562	10,088,861	4,777,313	3,390,692	1,111,826	1,248,197	592,767	8,135,460
	2018	-263,807	10,487,010	4,763,757	3,572,665	1,799,747	1,090,183	739,277	7,935,532
	2019	168,508	10,981,383	6,927,177	4,994,797	2,058,712	885,989	702,810	8,031,796
	2020	158,793	11,368,517	7,051,806	5,111,482	1,897,562	52,063	725,449	8,042,994
	2021	1,073,393	13,486,815	9,559,079	6,021,075	2,563,571	59,135	1,023,969	9,558,993
	2022	1,585,978	15,453,585	12,288,893	7,511,096	1,951,516	73,196	1,401,426	11,119,384
	2023	370,563	20,553,079	12,704,274	7,634,375	5,553,164	384,066	2,226,251	11,195,299
Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc	2014	11,908,690	97,287,804	94,103,677	72,369,075	23,609,260	42,083,720	14,047,767	58,526,202
	2015	12,659,855	106,671,333	100,092,221	77,257,074	24,531,108	49,064,149	14,035,388	66,386,057
	2016	14,198,693	175,936,048	167,409,161	141,924,887	85,521,443	54,628,911	45,648,975	74,584,750
	2017	37,882,609	196,064,664	198,120,639	145,582,161	71,913,340	70,895,546	44,779,483	99,207,358
	2018	25,830,941	178,523,711	146,549,176	104,589,978	51,428,633	91,025,731	31,499,654	107,180,126
	2019	24,102,816	198,129,122	158,104,577	117,770,404	59,304,650	107,014,317	30,194,027	118,082,942
	2020	31,370,659	259,280,544	206,360,656	153,153,524	116,227,957	39,371,894	51,568,627	125,302,902
	2021	22,660,116	349,382,869	276,054,781	225,846,208	190,108,668	46,302,270	54,153,133	129,830,169
	2022	54,346,390	490,969,836	403,245,988	311,282,950	271,527,073	106,797,356	43,387,050	172,029,685
	2023	-71,999,460	601,040,524	441,452,953	355,149,111	485,598,318	131,569,672	47,061,249	81,809,910
Flour Mill of Nigeria Plc	2014	10,437,522	220,087,648	245,701,366	216,422,044	26,528,831	46,678,382	45,371,104	98,943,111
	2015	2,419,544	231,529,876	229,777,869	204,834,346	31,517,578	71,918,940	47,921,200	96,651,666
	2016	10,425,786	233,296,607	247,876,504	223,664,917	29,046,061	66,504,239	37,257,683	100,244,139
	2017	9,829,046	343,933,157	375,225,284	324,918,838	55,801,512	80,823,655	63,597,671	108,115,699
	2018	9,244,729	322,604,582	371,370,740	321,920,291	40,126,542	49,546,925	71,755,238	151,446,296
	2019	19,317,654	314,058,187	370,205,529	337,073,874	66,343,291	50,322,189	68,230,014	138,929,273
	2020	12,582,571	314,267,060	394,884,217	354,952,741	68,333,644	28,471,323	61,693,906	146,316,890
	2021	20,172,489	380,322,525	535,881,585	478,166,108	77,584,189	23,160,406	76,980,128	159,878,794

	2022	21,819,816	487,617,576	832,810,561	768,739,096	155,202,371	43,782,434	155,480,370	174,663,847
	2023	14,173,904	719,285,322	923,015,713	795,330,687	244,339,315	97,817,112	151,925,626	181,820,527
Guinness Nigeria Plc	2014	9,573,480	132,328,273	109,202,120	57,868,906	30,723,577	19,218,236	13,469,248	45,061,717
	2015	7,794,899	122,246,632	118,495,882	62,604,362	31,482,313	15,503,824	10,750,598	48,341,376
	2016	-2,015,886	136,992,444	101,973,030	60,162,617	37,529,981	26,509,663	13,021,248	41,660,605
	2017	1,923,720	146,038,216	125,919,817	77,604,513	43,052,618	22,966,508	23,094,499	42,943,015
	2018	6,717,605	153,254,968	142,975,792	94,350,387	31,175,725	23,890,304	19,032,362	87,588,174
	2019	5,483,732	160,792,627	131,498,373	91,369,145	31,921,108	26,018,700	25,180,431	89,060,462
	2020	-12,578,818	144,145,581	104,376,015	71,045,954	31,944,466	18,718,953	26,426,253	73,038,140
	2021	1,255,338	169,406,525	160,416,257	114,706,338	61,675,534	14,019,385	21,460,505	74,286,575
	2022	15,651,362	215,660,208	206,822,127	134,159,371	69,682,989	14,078,900	32,000,675	89,979,391
	2023	-18,168,041	241,748,144	229,440,861	151,307,788	111,236,084	13,213,407	34,469,527	56,424,616
Honeywell Flour Mill Plc	2014	3,351,564	63,830,440	55,084,305	37,788,322	1,262,714	6,868,962	10,009,275	20,605,288
	2015	1,120,267	67,943,444	49,057,511	44,626,674	1,309,256	5,874,818	11,287,037	20,315,834
	2016	-3,023,852	76,046,576	50,883,780	46,522,386	3,117,770	1,169,430	5,586,084	16,362,599
	2017	4,304,955	113,151,714	53,227,891	40,515,269	7,478,658	871,697	4,515,525	52,334,665
	2018	4,426,978	124,835,013	71,476,319	55,423,670	12,331,422	6,518,925	7,844,965	56,391,664
	2019	68,368	137,505,112	74,409,113	62,899,939	20,443,802	6,076,164	14,103,285	56,667,969
	2020	650,492	142,261,292	80,450,397	66,588,559	21,487,123	5,008,244	17,525,888	57,160,022
	2021	1,125,864	147,394,656	109,594,730	93,973,456	23,799,441	3,245,255	19,780,169	57,968,678
	2022	-9,757,623	148,696,031	136,427,507	124,860,338	26,890,593	3,288,640	31,725,805	45,447,663
	2023	256,113	164,999,977	147,350,739	137,822,539	44,838,812	1,258,365	32,056,412	32,976,289
Austin Laz & Company Plc	2014	158,942	2,041,290	615,730	606,033	38,770	328,273	158,050	1,789,882
	2015	59,092	1,867,988	261,055	227,313	16,235	242,004	239,866	1,730,790
	2016	-146,126	1,760,775	217,428	208,261	13,914	180,819	360,418	1,584,664
	2017	315	1,699,093	312,730	193,655	11,925	56,575	63,267	1,584,979
	2018	-16,230	1,658,701	393,038	299,722	7,942	31,982	40,490	1,568,749
	2019	-84,368	1,533,853	205,757	236,482	1,857	22,261	25,830	1,484,381
	2020	-142,139	1,391,714	0	0	1,857	22,261	25,830	1,342,242
	2021	-44,568	1,347,146	0	0	1,857	22,261	25,830	1,297,674
	2022	-44,568	1,302,578	0	0	1,857	22,261	25,830	1,253,106
	2023	-44,568	1,302,578	0	0	1,857	22,261	25,830	1,253,106
Beta Glass	2014	2,390,223	26,928,387	16,632,879	12,184,227	6,315,973	12,009,592	2,295,922	15,952,981
	2015	1,991,127	27,171,069	15,953,224	12,247,347	4,386,369	8,014,021	3,479,878	17,578,125
	2016	3,799,393	33,184,130	19,091,192	15,145,377	5,341,684	10,385,530	4,210,668	21,474,964
	2017	4,115,142	38,211,613	22,186,258	16,938,395	5,282,430	14,377,983	5,025,216	25,145,114
	2018	5,052,805	46,079,629	26,321,014	19,940,375	11,598,037	13,438,292	6,239,740	29,627,573
	2019	5,580,220	52,080,362	29,412,252	21,474,020	9,086,710	13,729,988	6,544,848	34,558,001
	2020	3,466,670	53,963,634	25,637,010	19,733,028	8,178,695	12,746,846	7,454,229	37,189,718
	2021	5,457,671	63,112,410	36,982,815	27,729,399	11,853,395	15,476,340	9,179,179	42,127,418

	2022	4,685,414	75,944,552	54,340,363	43,830,778	13,950,402	26,131,329	9,617,231	46,263,350
	2023	6,442,223	106,851,898	62,905,451	50,518,011	23,257,755	28,500,192	17,743,383	52,005,006
Berger Paints Nigeria Plc	2014	148,808	3,640,145	3,082,930	1,736,060	401,484	480,049	523,921	2,459,830
	2015	330,316	3,895,870	3,022,264	1,643,696	447,539	266,060	459,526	2,587,330
	2016	224,007	4,102,265	2,602,824	1,491,193	679,151	381,029	569,475	2,604,181
	2017	246,276	4,311,424	3,092,445	1,819,368	557,396	175,390	574,991	2,641,145
	2018	320,509	4,535,299	3,377,223	1,896,862	622,491	190,982	606,712	2,813,052
	2019	448,733	5,066,449	3,584,804	1,920,480	804,589	330,541	812,048	3,073,400
	2020	146,028	4,971,872	3,837,582	2,418,504	704,369	317,381	702,294	3,146,972
	2021	135,635	5,110,669	4,964,796	3,382,076	918,785	305,517	1,166,616	3,230,703
	2022	208,670	5,528,528	6,331,634	4,326,316	1,226,474	243,351	1,366,787	3,323,445
	2023	468,797	6,610,970	7,910,181	5,214,061	1,409,786	310,035	2,148,260	3,531,401
Dangote Cement Plc	2014	185,814	963,441	371,534	128,584	73,785	2,932	36,315	638,542
	2015	213,171	1,124,475	389,215	130,418	79,584	4,252	38,369	748,479
	2016	368,205	1,502,564	426,129	178,129	178,567	11,857	55,850	981,367
	2017	254,630	1,611,087	552,364	158,594	142,737	12,340	62,259	991,017
	2018	481,456	1,721,974	618,301	170,288	92,879	11,046	59,820	1,293,548
	2019	261,349	1,825,076	610,247	181,009	130,939	12,700	67,736	1,282,249
	2020	352,609	2,116,060	719,945	225,744	140,245	14,829	54,545	1,352,377
	2021	381,100	2,582,298	993,399	345,225	214,411	15,798	88,421	1,461,472
	2022	402,857	2,658,463	1,205,401	455,122	154,463	16,842	132,704	1,491,535
	2023	490,323	3,070,468	1,297,639	623,159	217,387	33,076	187,799	1,602,964
Chemical and Allied Products Plc	2014	1,662,426	3,080,882	6,987,604	3,389,918	726,072	330,188	5,803,030	1,180,573
	2015	1,739,559	3,409,300	7,056,876	3,468,911	550,672	131,089	679,193	1,520,133
	2016	1,603,357	4,915,999	6,813,984	3,501,501	1,176,078	627,520	933,886	2,283,490
	2017	1,498,730	5,013,990	7,113,950	3,863,985	1,130,834	110,700	1,187,405	2,242,220
	2018	2,029,343	6,311,246	7,670,315	4,034,561	1,559,016	172,488	884,115	2,808,939
	2019	1,742,088	6,760,961	8,410,650	4,437,688	1,801,552	371,696	1,050,103	2,521,684
	2020	1,223,124	8,526,076	8,876,191	5,133,999	2,200,976	461,491	967,065	3,744,808
	2021	1,122,583	12,115,919	14,207,818	9,649,521	5,664,919	551,593	5,484,222	4,409,788
	2022	2,376,208	13,406,204	19,208,470	11,594,947	3,350,598	868,135	5,100,796	6,599,601
	2023	2,514,737	15,373,521	23,890,279	14,878,476	4,141,179	948,385	5,019,523	7,969,707
Cutix	2014	207,116	1,744,670	2,234,959	1,593,424	119,135	493,036	437,060	699,703
	2015	149,209	1,968,813	2,358,412	1,719,404	79,155	427,034	616,009	743,711
	2016	190,551	1,891,720	2,835,862	2,102,510	163,378	477,457	487,959	870,217
	2017	257,497	2,329,792	3,675,712	2,670,066	315,504	323,792	1,103,158	1,013,969
	2018	440,295	2,836,262	5,057,374	3,536,685	499,300	525,058	1,317,958	1,299,292
	2019	477,070	2,861,339	5,434,107	3,789,320	145,048	248,371	1,579,698	1,613,091
	2020	393,053	3,627,990	5,025,500	3,583,531	264,065	744,764	1,782,971	1,805,638
	2021	601,627	4,801,452	6,745,521	5,004,162	555,468	1,222,441	2,400,683	2,214,333
	2022	790,467	5,086,471	7,852,391	5,732,426	685,648	1,160,583	2,718,392	2,767,160

	2023	792,132	5,796,790	9,225,071	6,946,005	648,972	1,565,008	2,954,063	3,232,801
Eterna Plc	2014	1,258,798	18,048,814	82,832,117	79,545,456	6,127,093	6,101,462	2,905,174	8,011,847
	2015	1,263,884	27,845,708	92,669,238	89,735,520	12,524,638	18,365,420	1,217,501	9,261,791
	2016	1,523,153	31,101,289	107,536,032	99,120,141	10,581,931	13,283,455	4,068,467	10,451,307
	2017	2,069,846	47,154,881	173,611,081	167,390,078	23,802,855	27,908,580	6,487,073	12,108,066
	2018	1,139,517	52,690,694	251,874,722	247,341,686	23,351,490	30,976,733	8,075,026	12,699,750
	2019	-48,603	28,310,175	229,274,785	224,436,229	4,907,284	9,835,357	5,255,550	12,325,110
	2020	1,017,516	35,792,315	58,715,576	53,363,485	8,294,213	13,228,041	6,858,012	13,342,626
	2021	-1,078,546	46,080,961	82,197,987	78,192,664	11,292,725	12,960,126	12,019,495	12,133,665
	2022	1,157,705	54,363,612	116,472,441	107,667,859	11,939,950	17,669,039	11,126,474	13,291,371
	2023	-9,268,196	60,462,816	183,282,139	166,564,497	12,234,727	10,168,724	27,167,668	3,827,553
JAPPAUL OIL PLC	2014	-2,703,739	38,188,346	7,338,911	3,905,333	1,414,534	14,623,211	120,836	14,043,684
	2015	-6,969,887	35,022,432	5,434,086	3,598,943	1,739,999	12,351,478	0	7,052,411
	2016	-21,760,633	39,028,011	649,145	1,729,784	11,099,306	17,328,315	0	-14,666,782
	2017	-10,644,678	29,054,179	191,383	1,172,035	4,582,701	8,462,546	34,000	-25,266,052
	2018	-6,040,810	25,620,330	368,962	1,325,595	5,551,864	8,242,946	0	-31,316,275
	2019	40,687,874	26,937,078	85,853	1,054,492	11,379,904	18,191,479	0	9,379,852
	2020	-458,379	18,776,757	185,203	459,840	4,166,977	10,486,959	0	8,918,250
	2021	-2,998,714	17,517,415	226,439	625,902	4,437,518	10,484,869	0	5,917,615
	2022	-8,733,044	8,772,295	1,186,676	1,025,920	4,435,627	1,915,975	0	-2,815,429
	2023	-399,925	9,890,844	2,346,439	1,123,034	4,285,716	2,932,459	0	-3,215,354
MRS Oil Nigeria Plc	2014	746,404	57,846,626	92,325,405	85,366,807	17,328,018	20,636,012	3,822,749	20,218,121
	2015	935,625	66,893,741	87,099,216	80,676,760	21,226,030	20,519,974	6,260,483	20,977,324
	2016	1,465,905	81,364,815	109,635,054	100,879,939	32,156,838	43,244,878	7,004,173	22,163,841
	2017	1,385,056	62,190,318	107,088,347	99,393,668	24,232,833	34,234,991	5,289,372	23,109,497
	2018	-1,264,941	54,283,202	89,552,819	85,256,239	18,089,739	25,238,284	4,473,289	20,720,698
	2019	-1,704,010	44,209,648	64,909,370	61,160,282	18,408,455	17,999,700	6,180,329	19,107,616
	2020	-2,264,145	36,659,094	41,981,439	38,523,436	16,982,078	12,364,105	3,831,314	16,843,471
	2021	339,873	37,205,315	71,976,255	66,831,653	17,463,049	15,499,644	3,295,802	17,183,344
	2022	1,316,102	40,526,114	100,779,880	92,204,953	16,068,426	18,031,307	3,302,008	18,499,446
	2023	4,896,982	55,681,583	182,310,964	167,717,177	22,300,508	21,074,813	7,631,431	23,459,455
Nestle	2014	22,235,640	105,062,067	143,328,982	82,099,051	26,656,779	22,330,813	10,956,010	35,939,643
	2015	23,736,777	119,215,053	151,271,526	83,925,957	36,661,728	24,445,995	10,813,960	38,007,074
	2016	7,924,968	169,585,932	181,910,977	106,583,385	64,662,096	24,035,411	20,637,750	30,878,075
	2017	33,723,730	146,804,128	244,151,411	143,280,260	19,055,624	31,430,450	23,910,303	44,878,177
	2018	43,008,026	162,334,422	266,274,621	152,354,445	60,384,454	42,175,062	23,124,020	50,220,486
	2019	45,683,113	193,374,314	284,035,255	155,888,473	78,400,058	65,820,188	33,278,944	45,557,630
	2020	39,212,025	246,184,996	287,084,087	167,872,616	116,512,689	39,555,290	52,222,267	29,296,984
	2021	40,037,277	310,238,504	351,822,329	219,985,914	148,384,425	43,302,758	58,964,125	21,378,209
	2022	48,965,488	415,044,031	446,819,260	291,054,270	166,161,861	82,237,026	88,340,532	30,291,224

	2023	- 79,473,781	581,774,407	547,118,754	329,945,347	197,279,592	102,227,370	87,792,561	-78,035,156
unilever	2014	2,412,343	45,736,255	55,754,309	35,584,016	15,111,163	8,544,431	8,614,597	7,478,808
	2015	1,192,366	50,172,484	59,221,748	38,174,248	22,542,842	10,142,845	6,173,113	8,003,253
	2016	3,071,885	72,491,309	69,777,061	49,481,020	32,476,502	18,945,578	9,878,499	11,689,943
	2017	7,450,085	121,084,365	90,771,306	61,828,042	33,408,820	27,621,489	11,478,532	75,908,375
	2018	10,552,140	131,843,373	92,899,969	64,674,847	38,610,839	30,188,189	13,928,867	82,789,543
	2019	-7,419,674	103,677,519	60,486,835	55,737,010	34,719,709	24,131,026	11,869,295	66,528,350
	2020	-3,965,921	91,517,538	52,211,267	41,136,845	27,422,359	12,957,466	13,659,427	62,129,120
	2021	3,409,174	108,288,535	70,523,695	50,161,784	39,739,074	14,992,655	14,956,331	65,761,668
	2022	4,467,084	125,389,892	68,637,363	42,036,756	51,962,483	10,034,726	16,331,854	67,564,716
	2023	8,439,895	116,302,344	103,879,730	67,855,456	32,075,796	12,284,377	13,021,361	74,509,103
menichol	2014	40,538,746	378,273,496	519,799,955	376,201,848	104,015,816	58,368,489	28,985,847	22,947,942
	2015	60,337,718	420,149,791	1,009,806,763	811,062,216	108,462,478	49,106,875	62,639,409	260,454,358
	2016	57,848,754	475,140,932	1,093,805,288	903,245,896	127,931,224	55,689,201	77,061,730	301,533,497
	2017	38,227,647	539,237,536	967,193,655	820,939,405	128,733,750	77,702,055	42,812,271	325,778,733
	2018	39,240,912	825,689,552	786,912,331	646,582,896	62,548,205	93,409,117	51,756,675	333,152,614
	2019	17,128,307	722,521,934	643,380,590	541,016,023	56,393,332	93,951,117	49,683,912	346,419,982
	2020	17,781,575	711,959,366	732,091,283	607,238,875	73,853,018	96,654,673	148,688,051	353,732,001
	2021	14,296,405	692,513,155	773,559,018	661,343,273	72,317,373	102,574,618	129,973,012	359,155,370
	2022	19,761,187	653,717,275	834,017,681	704,653,775	59,855,096	114,166,014	92,610,215	380,436,700
	2023	36,065,800	1,068,653,149	1,594,612,866	1,404,624,841	293,826,739	165,970,869	275,371,990	591,649,477
septat	2014	40,481	444,026	124,377	50,647	71,924	195,480	10,027	259,658
	2015	12,993	545,198	112,972	63,705	74,572	161,310	16,398	280,976
	2016	-124,412	2,235,709	202,446	157,333	282,119	1,069,003	102,608	1,282,158
	2017	265,230	2,614,630	452,179	240,059	410,593	310,345	100,336	1,503,097
	2018	146,576	2,526,565	746,140	354,926	284,565	136,393	102,554	1,600,885
	2019	277,008	3,271,110	697,777	302,039	468,804	486,762	84,508	1,803,939
	2020	-85,322	3,449,573	530,467	405,892	343,340	254,671	74,570	1,664,045
	2021	117,176	3,163,369	733,188	447,999	367,058	255,557	74,957	1,707,486
	2022	104,706	3,537,257	951,795	487,059	459,869	389,431	55,406	1,759,883
	2023	123,872	3,395,019	1,061,271	529,275	533,845	410,165	52,428	1,793,027
Vita foam	2014	659,891	11,032,131	15,519,856	10,547,522	3,357,918	3,428,411	3,719,059	3,747,004
	2015	196,640	1,734,739	15,155,102	10,931,006	3,635,386	4,696,606	3,033,468	3,802,832
	2016	412,386	13,022,684	12,189,558	8,214,891	1,936,224	3,614,806	3,254,293	4,299,252
	2017	190,540	12,974,483	15,921,022	11,794,251	2,550,743	3,125,248	3,933,630	4,463,206
	2018	486,120	15,156,727	17,612,291	12,786,289	2,208,997	3,229,442	4,539,794	4,822,994
	2019	1,574,909	12,358,342	20,330,040	12,902,974	1,516,022	2,354,476	4,361,266	5,932,044
	2020	3,456,694	19,802,249	21,521,097	12,352,577	1,975,665	2,149,102	3,820,207	8,687,013
	2021	4,384,859	29,693,840	32,007,979	20,764,431	1,943,128	2,384,844	6,509,003	12,401,122
	2022	4,411,111	36,913,111	42,128,595	29,716,114	3,894,901	2,774,988	11,003,143	15,013,073
	2023	2,418,992	46,639,816	47,723,375	32,964,200	4,352,901	3,175,840	11,734,948	16,178,032

Total	2014	5,290,458	95,512,428	240,618,693	212,714,398	58,831,485	35,789,392	19,826,763	15,930,170
	2015	4,047,051	83,653,555	208,027,688	182,682,250	48,260,504	24,630,820	173,911,520	16,242,481
	2016	14,797,096	136,928,160	290,952,520	241,850,724	95,678,681	48,497,566	34,902,844	23,570,097
	2017	8,019,298	107,981,873	288,062,650	258,766,772	63,419,933	32,726,367	26,666,240	28,225,551
	2018	7,960,893	132,520,783	307,987,896	273,202,676	61,583,881	52,007,770	30,045,177	30,730,888
	2019	2,278,979	133,787,731	292,177,202	257,125,843	57,178,455	45,434,587	33,642,490	28,319,784
	2020	2,063,385	143,612,885	204,721,463	173,974,052	73,485,400	41,335,763	21,619,936	28,150,979
	2021	16,862,130	208,728,966	341,316,345	286,316,055	134,545,293	63,966,447	29,202,091	41,619,305
	2022	16,118,376	307,815,723	482,470,780	422,286,679	190,091,170	111,391,821	59,275,749	50,286,810
	2023	12,912,544	375,114,673	635,951,600	554,131,894	214,105,902	152,113,177	73,906,481	56,077,742
Northern	2014	233,545	3,262,150	13,509,406	12,806,618	1,080,453	461,144	1,584,937	1,773,912
	2015	-199,558	4,934,766	10,529,075	102,772,982	3,041,678	2,830,178	427,714	1,480,063
	2016	0	1,739,760	979,038	1,079,755	315,275	287,794	396,133	1,250,937
	2017	-16,234	4,337,444	940,521	967,784	479,235	437,433	1,367,418	1,239,578
	2018	-60,988	5,917,639	2,861,752	2,149,621	679,050	459,476	2,673,752	1,174,262
	2019	-31,696	4,992,912	4,149,917	3,569,622	542,929	133,550	2,176,922	1,150,712
	2020	64,635	8,491,986	8,841,135	7,965,077	3,115,124	824,685	1,560,582	2,768,993
	2021	69,919	7,365,270	8,667,751	7,874,781	1,768,304	9,610	3,206,326	2,787,771
	2022	80,668	13,315,128	15,232,820	14,161,127	9,401,278	177,456	8,237,924	2,854,469
	2023	272,820	17,827,833	16,161,840	15,014,793	9,813,215	668,456	7,645,092	6,579,567

COMPUTATION OF VARIABLES

Company	Year	ROA	ROE	ACP	APP	ITP	CCC	logACP	logAPP	logITP	logCCC
Cardbury Nigeria Plc	2014	0.04002928	0.09045840	72.87559	193.63539	39.45899	81.30081	1.862582	2.286985	1.596146	0
	2015	0.07681237	0.17397373	67.76811	213.37728	37.21018	108.39899	1.831025	2.329148	1.570662	0
	2016	0.01043342	0.02680747	60.49407	198.65522	79.26994	58.89120	1.781713	2.2981	1.899109	0
	2017	0.01055472	0.02554742	53.95997	126.11075	88.99104	16.84027	1.732072	2.100752	1.949346	1.226349
	2018	0.02989988	0.06493180	38.25351	130.49774	76.40832	15.83592	1.582671	2.115603	1.883141	#NUM!
	2019	0.03717962	0.07893458	42.04076	113.23360	71.37981	0.18697	1.623671	2.053975	1.853575	-0.72823
	2020	0.02805805	0.06877194	39.74763	134.95074	64.86576	30.33735	1.599311	2.130175	1.812015	#NUM!
	2021	0.01029365	0.03297890	34.91616	183.34231	82.37403	66.05212	1.543026	2.263263	1.91579	0
	2022	0.00976512	0.04383427	34.13918	157.44421	91.56293	31.74211	1.533253	2.197127	1.96172	#NUM!
	2023	0.30095218	2.93071042	33.24208	147.81738	69.12459	45.45070	1.521688	2.169726	1.839633	0
Champion Breweries Plc	2014	0.07865857	0.12852940	63.8236	330.98878	48.56968	218.59550	1.804981	2.519813	1.686365	0
	2015	0.00746818	0.01083178	70.57476	445.97097	51.07555	324.32066	1.848649	2.649307	1.708213	0
	2016	0.05324528	0.06914336	23.81526	167.11761	69.19488	74.10748	1.376855	2.223022	1.840074	0
	2017	0.05130034	0.06361804	95.36572	119.68545	63.80997	39.49024	1.979392	2.078041	1.804889	0
	2018	0.02515560	0.03324377	83.53004	183.87049	75.52796	24.81249	1.921843	2.264512	1.878108	0
	2019	0.01534488	0.02098011	46.68366	150.44253	51.35857	52.40029	1.669165	2.177371	1.710613	0
	2020	0.01396778	0.01974302	2.69477	135.50084	51.80276	81.00331	0.430522	2.131942	1.714353	0
	2021	0.07958832	0.11229143	2.257987	155.40471	62.07341	91.07331	0.353721	2.191464	1.792906	0
	2022	0.10262848	0.14263182	2.17404	94.83348	68.10198	24.55746	0.337267	1.976962	1.83316	#NUM!
	2023	0.01802956	0.03309988	11.0344	265.49716	106.4372	148.025	1.042749	2.42406	2.027094	0

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Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc	201 4	0.1224068 1	0.203476 21	163.23 02	119.0754 5	70.851 19	115.005 90	2.2128	2.07582 2	1.850347	2.06072
	201 5	0.1186809 5	0.190700 51	178.91 91	115.8968 9	66.31	129.332 26	2.252657	2.06407 2	1.821579	2.111707
	201 6	0.0807037 2	0.190369 92	119.10 67	219.9425 9	117.39 93	16.5633	2.075936	2.34230 9	2.069665	0
	201 7	0.1932148 7	0.381852 82	130.61 17	180.2993 5	112.27	62.5823 7	2.115982	2.25599 4	2.050264	1.796452
	201 8	0.1446919 3	0.241004 95	226.71 16	179.4765 8	109.92 81	157.163 04	2.355474	2.25400 8	2.041109	2.19635
	201 9	0.1216520 6	0.204117 68	247.05 31	183.7999 7	93.578 86	156.831 98	2.39279	2.26434 5	1.971178	0
	202 0	0.1209911 8	0.250358 60	69.638 96	276.9979 0	122.89 99	84.4590 6	1.842852	2.44247 6	2.089551	0
	202 1	0.0648575 5	0.174536 60	61.220 92	307.2429 9	87.519 26	158.502 80	1.7869	2.48748 2	1.942104	0
	202 2	0.1106919 1	0.315912 86	96.668 13	318.3835 9	50.874 21	170.841 25	1.985283	2.50295 1	1.706498	0
	202 3	- 0.1197913 6	- 0.880082 38	108.78 38	499.0675 2	48.366 6	341.917 12	2.036564	2.69815 9	1.684546	0
Flour Mill of Nigeria Plc	201 4	0.0474243 9	0.105490 13	69.342 75	44.74139	76.519 25	101.120 62	1.841001	1.65070 9	1.883771	2.00484
	201 5	0.0104502 5	0.025033 65	114.24 26	56.16205	85.392 11	143.472 63	2.057828	1.74944 3	1.931418	2.156769
	201 6	0.0446889 7	0.104003 95	97.927 99	47.40043	60.801 02	111.328 58	1.990907	1.67578 2	1.783911	2.046607
	201 7	0.0285783 6	0.090912 29	78.621 13	62.68504	71.442 92	87.3790 0	1.895539	1.79716 4	1.853959	1.941407
	201 8	0.0286565 3	0.061042 95	48.696 96	45.49632	81.357 6	84.5582 5	1.687502	1.65797 6	1.910398	1.927156
	201 9	0.0615097 9	0.139046 68	49.614 6	71.83975	73.882 78	51.6576 3	1.695609	1.85636 5	1.868543	1.713135
	202 0	0.0400378 3	0.085995 34	26.316 66	70.26789	63.440 21	19.4889 8	1.420231	1.84675 7	1.802365	1.289789
	202 1	0.0530404 8	0.126173 64	15.775 03	59.22258	58.761 48	15.3139 3	1.19797	1.77248 7	1.769093	1.185087
	202 2	0.0447478 0	0.124924 63	19.188 74	73.69063	73.822 62	19.3207 4	1.283047	1.86741 2	1.868189	1.286024
	202 3	0.0197055 4	0.077955 47	38.681 08	112.1343 0	69.723 02	-3.73020	1.587499	2.04973 8	1.843376	#NUM!
Guinness Nigeria Plc	201 4	0.0723464 4	0.212452 62	64.235 53	193.7846 5	84.955 39	44.5937 3	1.807775	2.28731 9	1.929191	0
	201 5	0.0637637 1	0.161246 94	47.756 05	183.5502 2	62.678 83	73.1153 3	1.679028	2.26375 5	1.797121	0
	201 6	- 0.0147153 1	- 0.048388 30	94.888 1	227.6902 8	78.998 48	53.8037 0	1.977212	2.35734 4	1.897619	0
	201 7	0.0131727 2	0.044797 04	66.572 33	202.4908 7	108.62 12	27.2973 9	1.823294	2.30640 5	2.035914	0
	201 8	0.0438328 7	0.076695 34	60.989 07	120.6051 2	73.627 81	14.0117 6	1.785252	2.08136 6	1.867042	1.146493
	201 9	0.0341043 7	0.061573 14	72.220 1	127.5179 3	100.59 04	45.2925 5	1.858658	2.10557 1	2.002556	1.656027

	2020	- 0.0872646 8	- 0.172222 59	65.459 65	164.1153 3	135.76 54	37.1097 3	1.815974	2.21514 9	2.132789	1.569488
	2021	0.0074102 1	0.016898 58	31.898 73	196.2539 3	68.288 16	96.0670 4	1.503773	2.29281 8	1.834345	0
	2022	0.0725741 8	0.173943 85	24.846 46	189.5826 6	87.062 47	77.6737 3	1.395265	2.27779 9	1.939831	0
	2023	- 0.0751527 6	- 0.321987 85	21.020 2	268.3349 7	83.150 89	164.163 88	1.322637	2.42867 7	1.919867	0
Honeywell Flour Mill Plc	2014	0.0525073 0	0.162655 53	45.515 16	12.19664	96.680 28	129.998 80	1.658156	1.08624	1.985338	2.113939
	2015	0.0164882 3	0.055142 56	43.710 1	10.70836	92.316 28	125.318 02	1.640582	1.02972 3	1.965278	2.098014
	2016	- 0.0397631 6	- 0.184802 67	8.3885 66	24.46104	43.826 66	27.7541 8	0.923688	1.38847 5	1.641738	1.443328
	2017	0.0380458 7	0.082258 19	5.9774 94	67.37485	40.680 14	20.7172 2	0.776519	1.82849 8	1.609382	#NUM!
	2018	0.0354626 3	0.078504 12	33.289 45	81.21023	51.664 07	3.74329	1.522307	1.90961 1	1.713189	0.573254
	2019	0.0004972 0	0.001206 47	29.805 49	118.6326 7	81.839 49	-6.98769	1.474296	2.07420 4	1.912963	#NUM!
	2020	0.0045725 2	0.011380 19	22.722 19	117.7799 9	96.066 79	1.00899	1.35645	2.07107 2	1.982573	0.003886
	2021	0.0076384 3	0.019421 94	10.808 17	92.43883	76.827 67	-4.80299	1.033752	1.96585 4	1.885518	#NUM!
	2022	- 0.0656212 7	- 0.214700 21	8.7984 72	78.60836	92.742 97	22.9330 8	0.944407	1.89546 9	1.967281	1.360462
	2023	0.0015522 0	0.007766 58	3.1170 74	118.7481 1	84.896 06	30.7349 8	0.493747	2.07462 7	1.928888	#NUM!
Austin Laz & Company Plc	2014	0.0778635 1	0.088800 27	194.59 77	23.35030	95.189 95	266.437 36	2.289138	1.36829 2	1.978591	2.425595
	2015	0.0316340 4	0.034141 63	338.36 34	26.06879	385.15 65	697.451 17	2.529383	1.41612 1	2.585637	2.843514
	2016	- 0.0829895 9	- 0.092212 61	303.54 39	631.6716 5	631.67 17	303.543 86	2.482221	2.80049 1	2.800491	2.482221
	2017	0.0001853 9	0.000198 74	66.031	119.2453 3	119.24 53	66.0310 0	1.819748	2.07644 1	2.076441	1.819748
	2018	0.0097847 7	0.010345 82	29.700 51	9.67173	49.308 53	69.3373 1	1.472764	0.98550 4	1.692922	1.840967
	2019	- 0.0550039 7	- 0.056837 16	39.489 62	2.86620	39.867 52	76.4909 3	1.596483	0.45730 7	1.600619	1.88361
	2020	- 0.1021323 3	- 0.105896 70	#DIV/0 !	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2021	- 0.0330832 7	- 0.034344 53	#DIV/0 !	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2022	- 0.0342152 3	- 0.035566 03	#DIV/0 !	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	2023	-	-	#DIV/0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

	3	0.0342152 3	0.035566 03	!									
Beta Glass	201 4	0.0887622 0	0.149829 24	263.54 43	189.2061 1	68.778 39	143.116 62		2.27693 5	1.837452		0	
	201 5	0.0732811 4	0.113273 00	183.35 59	130.7242 0	103.70 86	156.340 31	2.420854	2.11635 6	2.015815	2.194071		
	201 6	0.1144942 8	0.176921 97	198.55 85	128.7333 2	101.47 61	171.301 28	2.263295	2.10969 1	2.006364	2.233761		
	201 7	0.1076934 9	0.163655 73	236.54 12	113.8293 8	108.28 68	230.998 57	2.297888	2.05625 4	2.034575	2.363609		
	201 8	0.1096537 7	0.170544 01	186.35 21	212.2970 9	114.21 58	88.2707 9	2.373907	2.32694 4	2.057726		0	
	201 9	0.1071463 4	0.161474 04	170.38 63	154.4493 8	111.24 46	127.181 58	2.270334	2.231435	2.18878 6	2.046279	2.104424	
	202 0	0.0642408 6	0.093215 82	181.47 98	151.2805 7	137.88 02	168.079 39	2.22541 4	2.258828	2.17978 3	2.139502	2.225514	
	202 1	0.0864754 0	0.129551 52	152.74 29	156.0253 5	120.82 48	117.542 44	2.183961	2.19319 5	2.082156	2.070195		
	202 2	0.0616952 0	0.101277 02	175.52 21	116.1717 2	80.087 31	139.437 71	2.244332	2.0651	1.903564	2.14438		
	202 3	0.0602911 4	0.123876 98	165.36 83	168.0406 7	128.19 85	125.526 20	2.218452	2.22541 4	2.107883	2.098734		
Berger Paints Nigeria Plc	201 4	0.0408796 9	0.060495 24	56.834 86	84.41048	110.15 24	82.5767 7	1.754615	1.92639 6	2.041994	1.916858		
	201 5	0.0847862 0	0.127666 75	32.132 17	99.38075	102.04 26	34.7940 1	1.50694	1.99730 2	2.008781	1.541504		
	201 6	0.0546056 9	0.086018 21	53.432 57	166.2361 0	139.39 07	26.5871 3	1.727806	2.22072 5	2.144234	1.424671		
	201 7	0.0571217 3	0.093245 92	20.701 21	111.8242 9	115.35 42	24.2311 0	1.315996	2.04853 6	2.062033	1.384373		
	201 8	0.0706698 7	0.113936 39	20.640 75	119.7816 3	116.74 54	17.6045 1	1.314726	2.07839	2.06724	1.245624		
	201 9	0.0885695 3	0.146005 40	33.655 25	152.9174 9	154.33 51	35.0728 8	1.527053	2.18445 7	2.188465	1.544971		
	202 0	0.0293708 3	0.046402 70	30.186 73	106.3031 9	105.99	29.8735 8	1.479816	2.02654 6	2.025265	1.475287		
	202 1	0.0265395 8	0.041983 12	22.460 88	99.15700	125.90 34	49.2072 7	1.351427	1.99632 3	2.100037	1.692029		
	202 2	0.0377442 2	0.062787 26	14.028 47	103.4744 1	115.31 23	25.8663 1	1.14701	2.01483 3	2.061875	1.412734		
	202 3	0.0709119 8	0.132751 00	14.305 97	98.68927	150.38 47	66.0013 7	1.155517	1.99427	2.177204	1.819553		
Dangote Cement Plc	201 4	0.1928649 5	0.290997 30	2.8804 36	209.4469 4	103.08 42	103.482 33	0.459458	2.32107 4	2.013192		0	
	201 5	0.1895738 0	0.284805 59	3.9874 62	222.7312 2	107.38 31	111.360 69	0.600697	2.34778 1	2.030936		0	
	201 6	0.2450511 3	0.375196 03	10.156 09	365.8975 0	114.44 09	241.300 47	1.006727	2.56335 9	2.058581		0	
	201 7	0.1580485 7	0.256938 07	8.1542 24	328.5055 2	143.28 75	177.063 82	0.911383	2.51654 3	2.156208		0	
	201 8	3.6309135 1	0.477988 45	6.5207 56	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	
	201 9	3.3713627 5	0.475919 26	7.5961 05	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	
	202 0	0.1666346 9	0.260732 77	7.5180 53	88.19249	0	80.6744 3	0	1.94543 2	0	0	0	

	202 1	0.1475817 3	0.260764 49	5.8045 86	93.48589	0	87.6813 0	0	1.97074 6	0	0
	202 2	0.1515375 6	3.035756 27	5.0998 22	123.8766 6	0	118.776 84	0.707555	2.09299	0	0
	202 3	0.1596899 9	2.610892 50	9.3036 2	127.3290 7	0	118.025 45	0.968652	2.10492 8	0	0
Chemical and Allied Products Plc	201 4	0.5395941 8	1.408151 80	17.247 49	78.17778	624.82 51	563.894 83	1.236726	1.89308 3	2.795758	2.751198
	201 5	0.5102393 5	1.144346 58	6.7802 64	57.94190	71.464 92	20.3032 9	0.831247	1.76299 3	1.854093	1.307566
	201 6	0.3261508 0	0.702151 97	33.613 93	122.5955 6	97.349 22	8.36759	1.526519	2.08847 5	1.988332	0.922601
	201 7	0.2989096 5	0.668413 45	5.6797 56	106.8209 1	112.16 47	11.0235 7	0.75433	2.02865 6	2.049856	1.042322
	201 8	0.3215439 6	0.722458 91	8.2080 23	141.0415 8	79.984 41	52.8491 4	0.914239	2.14934 7	1.903005	0
	201 9	0.2576687 0	0.690843 10	16.130 62	148.1777 2	86.371 01	45.6760 8	1.207651	2.17078 3	1.936368	0
	202 0	0.1434568 5	0.326618 61	18.977 08	156.4776 8	68.753 17	68.7474 2	1.278229	2.19445 2	1.837293	0
	202 1	0.0926535 6	0.254566 21	14.170 47	214.2795 9	207.44 46	7.33548	1.151384	2.33098 1	2.316902	0.865428
	202 2	0.1772468 9	0.360053 28	16.496 33	105.4742 4	160.56 91	71.5912 2	1.217387	2.02314 6	2.205662	1.85486
	202 3	0.1635758 7	0.315536 95	14.489 6	101.5917 4	123.13 94	36.0372 0	1.161056	2.00685 8	2.090397	1.556751
Cutix	201 4	0.1187135 7	0.296005 59	80.519 66	27.28983	100.11 58	153.345 62	1.905902	1.43600 1	2.000503	2.185671
	201 5	0.0757862 7	0.200627 66	66.089 98	16.80325	130.76 82	180.054 89	1.820136	1.22539 3	2.116502	2.255405
	201 6	0.1007289 7	0.218969 52	61.452 85	28.36275	84.710 67	117.800 77	1.788542	1.45274 8	1.927938	0
	201 7	0.1105236 0	0.253949 58	32.152 7	43.12963	150.80 25	139.825 59	1.507218	1.63477 6	2.178409	2.145587
	201 8	0.1552377 7	0.338873 02	37.894 4	51.52975	136.01 85	122.383 17	1.578575	1.71205 8	2.133598	2.087722
	201 9	0.1667296 3	0.295748 97	16.682 67	13.97151	152.16 18	154.872 97	1.222266	1.14524 3	2.182306	2.189976
	202 0	0.1083390 5	0.217680 95	54.091 9	26.89630	181.60 42	208.799 84	1.733132	1.42969 3	2.259126	2.31973
	202 1	0.1253010 5	0.271696 71	66.146 26	40.51544	175.10 41	200.734 92	1.820505	1.60762 1	2.243296	2.302623
	202 2	0.1554057 8	0.285660 03	53.946 98	43.65717	173.08 78	183.377 62	1.731967	1.64005 6	2.238266	2.263346
	202 3	0.1366501 1	0.245029 62	61.921 25	34.10230	155.23 07	183.049 61	1.79184	1.53278 4	2.190978	2.262569
Eterna Plc	201 4	0.0697440 8	0.157117 08	26.886 11	28.11460	13.330 6	12.1021 1	1.429528	1.44893 2	1.12485	0
	201 5	0.0453888 3	0.136462 16	72.336 61	50.94407	4.9521 96	26.3447 3	1.859358	1.70709 4	0.694798	0
	201 6	0.0489739 5	0.145738 04	45.086 85	38.96690	14.981 72	21.1016 7	1.65405	1.59069 6	1.175562	0
	201 7	0.0438946 3	0.170947 70	58.675 01	51.90297	14.145 29	20.9173 3	1.768453	1.71519 2	1.150612	0
	201	0.0216265	0.089727	44.889	34.45959	11.916	22.3460	1.652144	1.53731	1.076139	0

	8	3	51	41		25	6				
	2019	0.00171680	0.00394341	15.65765	7.98070	8.547086	16.22404	1.194727	0.902041	0.931818	1.210159
	2020	0.02842834	0.07626055	82.23091	56.73145	46.908	72.40746	1.915035	1.753824	1.671247	1.859783
	2021	0.02340546	0.08888872	57.54941	52.71396	56.10649	60.94195	1.760041	1.721926	1.749013	1.784916
	2022	0.02129559	0.08710200	55.37103	40.47709	37.71936	52.61330	1.743283	1.607209	1.576564	1.721096
	2023	0.15328753	2.42144158	20.25066	26.81049	59.53369	52.97386	1.306439	1.428305	1.774763	1.724062
JAPPAUL OIL PLC	2014	0.07080011	0.19252349	727.2839	132.20509	11.29357	606.37240	2.861704	2.121248	1.052831	0
	2015	0.19901208	0.98829847	829.6316	176.46838	0	653.16322	0	2.246667	0	0
	2016	0.55756449	1.48366786	9743.332	2,342.05351	0	7,401.27806	0	3.369597	0	0
	2017	0.36637339	0.42130357	16139.52	1,427.16375	10.58842	14,722.94224	4.207891	3.154474	0	0
	2018	0.23578190	0.19289682	8154.431	1,528.69493	0	6,625.73639	0	3.184321	0	0
	2019	1.51047838	4.33779488	77340.22	3,939.01989	0	73,401.19927	0	3.595388	0	0
	2020	0.02441204	0.05139786	20667.81	3,307.55612	0	17,360.25183	0	3.519507	0	0
	2021	0.17118473	0.50674368	16900.7	2,587.77583	0	14,312.92230	0	3.412927	0	0
	2022	0.99552557	3.10185197	589.3191	1,578.09952	0	988.78038	0	3.198134	0	0
	2023	0.04043386	0.12437977	456.1583	1,392.91094	0	936.75267	0	3.143923	0	0
MRS Oil Nigeria Plc	2014	0.01290316	0.03691758	81.58258	74.08883	16.3448	23.83855	1.911597	1.869753	1.21338	0
	2015	0.01398673	0.04460173	85.99148	96.03138	28.32385	18.28394	1.934455	1.982413	1.452152	0
	2016	0.01801645	0.06613948	143.972	116.34866	25.34224	52.96560	2.158278	2.065761	1.403845	0
	2017	0.02227125	0.05993449	116.6866	88.98941	19.42398	47.12114	2.067021	1.949338	1.288338	0
	2018	0.02330262	0.06104722	102.8664	77.44600	19.1511	44.57147	2.012273	1.888999	1.282194	0
	2019	0.03854385	0.08917962	101.2164	109.86029	36.88374	28.23982	2.005251	2.040841	1.566835	0
	2020	0.06176216	0.13442271	107.4975	160.90098	36.30075	17.10276	2.031398	2.206559	1.559916	0
	2021	0.0091350	0.019779	78.600	95.37416	17.999	1.22631	1.895425	1.97943	1.255272	0

	1	7	21	51		97			1		
	202	0.0324754	0.071142	65.304		13.071	14.7681		1.80351		
	2	1	78	97	63.60803	24	8	1.814946	2	1.116317	0
	202	0.0879461	0.208742	42.193		16.608	10.2692		1.68603	1.220321	0
	3	7	36	33	48.53221	15	7	1.625244			
Nestle	201										
	4	0.2116428	0.618693	56.867	118.5120	48.708	12.9358	-	2.07376		
		9	96	4	2	77	5	1.754863	2	1.687607	0
	201										
	5	0.1991088	0.624535	58.985	159.4444	47.030	53.4285	-	2.20260		
		9	76	25	8	69	5	1.770743	9	1.672381	0
	201										
	6	0.0467312	0.256653	48.226	221.4385	70.674	102.537	-	2.34525		
		8	56	47	0	98	05	1.683286	3	1.849266	0
	201										
7	0.2297192	0.751450	46.987		60.910	59.3547	-				
	2	53	7		48.54334	42	8	1.671984	1.68613	1.784692	0
201											
8	0.2649347	0.856384	57.812	144.6648	55.398	31.4538	-	1.762019	2.16036		0
	3	11	11	0	89	0			3	1.743501	
201											
9	0.2362418	1.002754	84.582	183.5672	77.919	21.0650	-	1.92728	2.26379		0
	9	38	35	7	9	2			5	1.891648	
202											
0	0.1592787	1.338432	50.290	253.3297	113.54	89.4938	-	1.701488	2.40368		0
	0	14	77	7	52	1			6	2.055169	
202											
1	0.1290532	1.872807	44.924	246.1990	97.833	103.441	-	1.652485	2.39128		0
	2	82	68	1	11	22			6	1.990486	
202											
2	0.1179766	1.616490	67.178	208.3772	110.78	30.4145	-	1.827228	2.31885	2.044479	0
	1	90	2	2	45	4					
202											
3	0.1366058	1.018435	68.199	218.2393	97.119	52.9202	-	1.833778	2.33893		0
	4	60	07	3	98	8			3	1.987309	
unilever	201										
	4	0.0527446	0.322557	55.936	155.0014	88.363	10.7011	-	2.19033		
		6	15	79	6	49	8	1.747698	6	1.946273	0
	201										
	5	0.0237653	0.148985	62.513	215.5415	59.023	94.0046	-	2.33353		
		4	17	16	7	72	9	1.795971	1	1.771027	0
	201										
	6	0.0423759	0.262780	99.103	239.5650	72.869	67.5923	-	2.37942		
		1	15	29	5	4	7	1.996088	3	1.862545	0
	201										
7	0.0615280	0.098145	111.06	197.2279	67.763	18.3961	-	2.29496			
	5	76	86	7	17	8	2.045591	9	1.830994	0	
201											
8	0.0800354	0.127457	118.60	217.9047	78.609	20.6874	-	2.33826			
	2	40	81	5	18	7	2.074114	7	1.895473	0	
201											
9	0.0715649	0.111526	145.61	227.3658	77.727	-4.02291	2.163208	2.35672			
	3	50	56	7	4			5	1.890574	0	
202											
0	0.0433350	0.063833	90.583	243.3137	121.19	31.5326	-	1.957049	2.38616		0
	9	53	42	7	77	6			7	2.083494	
202											
1	0.0314823	0.051841	77.595	289.1596	108.82	102.735	-	1.889836	2.46113		0
	2	36	47	1	91	06			8	2.036745	
202											
2	0.0356255	0.066115	53.362	451.1838	141.80	256.013	-	1.727238	2.65435		0
	5	63	7	7	75	68			4	2.151699	

	202 3	0.0725685 7	0.113273 34	43.163 35	172.5383 1	70.042 96	59.3320 0	-	1.635115	2.23688 6	1.845364	0
menichol	201 4	0.1071678 2	1.766552 57	40.985 96	100.9186 2	28.122 76	31.8099 1	-	1.612635	2.00397 1	1.449058	0
	201 5	0.1436100 2	0.231663 31	17.749 94	48.81106	28.189 43	-2.87168	1.249197	1.68851 8	1.450086	0	
	201 6	0.1217507 3	0.191848 52	18.583 34	51.69677	31.140 5	-1.97293	1.269124	1.71346 3	1.493326	0	
	201 7	0.0708920 4	0.117342 37	29.323 24	57.23665	19.034 87	-8.87853	1.467212	1.75767 4	1.27955	0	
	201 8	0.0475250 2	0.117786 59	43.326 72	35.30884	29.216 96	37.2348 3	1.636756	1.54788 4	1.465635	0	
	201 9	0.0237062 8	0.049443 76	53.299 96	38.04613	33.519 58	48.7734 0	1.726727	1.58031	1.525299	0	
	202 0	0.0249755 5	0.050268 49	48.189 29	44.39168	89.373 62	93.1712 3	1.68295	1.64730 2	1.951209	0	
	202 1	0.0206442 4	0.039805 63	48.399 33	39.91247	71.733 02	80.2198 8	1.684839	1.60110 9	1.855719	0	
	202 2	0.0302289 5	0.051943 43	49.963 68	31.00403	47.970 69	66.9303 4	1.698654	1.49141 8	1.680976	0	
	202 3	0.0337488 4	0.060958 05	37.990 02	76.35260	71.557 03	33.1944 4	1.579669	1.88282 4	1.854652	0	
	septat	201 4	0.0911680 8	0.155901 22	573.66 07	518.3379 1	72.262 03	127.584 85	2.758655	2.71461 3	1.85891	0
		201 5	0.0238317 1	0.046242 38	521.17 47	427.2628 5	93.952 91	187.864 77	2.716983	2.63069 5	1.97291	0
201 6		0.0556476 7	0.097033 28	1927.3 59	654.4935 6	238.04 24	1,510.90 769	3.284963	2.81590 5	2.376654	0	
201 7		0.1014407 4	0.176455 68	250.51 12	624.2900 5	152.55 68	221.221 97	2.398827	2.79538 6	2.183432	0	
201 8		0.0580139 4	0.091559 36	66.721 32	292.6419 2	105.46 48	120.455 77	1.824265	2.46633 7	2.023108	0	
201 9		0.0846831 8	0.153557 30	254.62 02	566.5277 0	102.12 4	209.783 52	2.405893	2.75322 1	2.009128	0	
202 0		0.0247340 8	0.051273 85	175.23 22	308.7498 6	67.057 37	66.4602 7	2.243614	2.48960 7	1.826447	0	
202 1		0.0370415 2	0.068624 87	127.22 29	299.0546 2	61.070 01	110.761 70	2.104565	2.47575 1	1.785828	0	
202 2		0.0296009 0	0.059496 00	149.34 13	344.6239 3	41.521 03	153.761 59	2.17418	2.53734 5	1.618268	0	
202 3		0.0364863 9	0.069085 41	141.06 69	368.1515 8	36.155 53	190.929 13	2.149425	2.56602 7	1.558175	0	
Vita foam		201 4	0.0598153 7	0.176111 63	80.630 26	116.2017 1	128.69 91	93.1276 5	1.906498	2.06521 3	2.109575	0
		201 5	0.1133542 3	0.051708 83	113.11 45	121.3901 0	101.29 13	93.0156 6	2.053518	2.08418 3	2.005572	0
	201 6	0.0316667 4	0.095920 41	108.24 05	86.02935	144.59 31	166.804 32	2.03439	1.93464 7	2.160148	0	
	201 7	0.0146857 5	0.042691 29	71.648 39	78.93856	121.73 52	114.444 98	1.855206	1.89728 9	2.085416	0	
	201 8	0.0320728	0.100792	66.927	63.05848	129.59	133.462	1.825605	1.79974	2.112584	0	

	8	9	16	48		39	89		3		
	2019	0.12743692	0.26549179	42.27162	42.88531	123.3717	122.75803	1.626049	1.632309	2.091216	0
	2020	0.17456068	0.39791514	36.44899	58.37792	112.8813	90.95242	1.561685	1.766249	2.052622	0
	2021	0.14766898	0.35358567	27.19535	34.15657	114.4161	107.45492	1.434495	1.533474	2.058487	0
	2022	0.11949984	0.29381799	24.04235	47.84067	135.1505	111.35217	1.380977	1.679797	2.130818	0
	2023	0.05186538	0.14952325	24.2896	48.19801	129.9366	106.02819	1.38542	1.683029	2.113731	0
Total	2014	0.05539026	0.33210305	54.28975	100.94988	34.02106	12.63907	1.734718	2.004106	1.531748	0
	2015	0.04837871	0.24916458	43.2166	96.42472	347.476	294.26792	1.635651	1.984188	2.540925	0
	2016	0.10806467	0.62779105	60.84021	144.39783	52.67521	30.88241	1.784191	2.159561	1.721606	0
	2017	0.07426522	0.28411484	41.4671	89.45614	37.61371	10.37532	1.617704	1.95161	1.575346	0
	2018	0.06007279	0.25905184	61.63501	82.27634	40.14049	19.49916	1.789827	1.915275	1.603583	0
	2019	0.01703429	0.08047304	56.75879	81.16701	47.75681	23.34858	1.754033	1.90938	1.679035	0
	2020	0.01436769	0.07329710	73.69796	154.17340	45.35893	35.11651	1.867455	2.188009	1.656663	0
	2021	0.08078481	0.40515165	68.40503	171.52036	37.22726	65.88807	1.835088	2.234316	1.570861	0
	2022	0.05236372	0.32052890	84.27042	164.30373	51.2345	28.79881	1.925675	2.215647	1.709563	0
	2023	0.03442292	0.23026148	87.3043	141.02898	48.68131	-5.04337	1.941036	2.149308	1.687362	0
Northern	2014	0.07159235	0.13165535	12.45929	30.79387	45.17211	26.83753	1.095493	1.488464	1.65487	0
	2015	0.04043920	0.13483075	98.1107	10.80257	1.519034	88.82717	1.991716	1.033527	0.181567	0
	2016	0.00000000	0.00000000	107.2939	106.57545	133.9087	134.62711	2.030575	2.027657	2.126809	0
	2017	0.00374276	0.01309639	169.7602	180.74361	515.7221	504.73867	2.229836	2.257063	2.712416	0
	2018	0.01030614	0.05193730	58.60352	115.30091	453.9961	397.29868	1.767924	2.061833	2.657052	0
	2019	0.00634820	0.02754469	11.7462	55.51543	222.594	178.82480	1.069897	1.744414	2.347514	0
	2020	0.00761129	0.02334242	34.04654	142.75069	71.51374	37.19042	1.532073	2.154578	1.854389	0
	2021	0.00949307	0.02508061	0.404678	81.96177	148.6148	67.05771	-0.39289	1.913611	2.172062	0
	2022	0.00605837	0.02826025	4.252098	242.31592	212.3307	25.73310	0.628603	2.384382	2.327013	0

	202										
	3	0.0153030	0.041464	15.096	238.5529	185.84	37.6092	-		2.37758	
		4	73	45	7	73	3	1.178875	5	2.269156	0

APPENDIX II
SPSS OUTPUT

Notes

Output Created		10-JUL-2024 06:51:44
Comments		
Input	Active Dataset	DataSet0
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	220
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	All non-missing data are used.
Syntax		DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=ROA ROE ACP APP ITP CCC /STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV MIN MAX.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.00
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.08

[DataSet0]

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
ROA	220	-1.00	3.63	.0846	.36644
ROE	220	-2.42	4.34	.2339	.59556
ACP	220	.00	77340.22	764.7430	5651.72581
APP	220	.00	3939.02	217.6438	448.66731
ITP	220	.00	631.67	87.8927	85.02435
CCC	220	-988.78	73401.20	634.9960	5290.25288
Valid N (listwise)	220				

CORRELATIONS

/VARIABLES=ROA ROE ACP APP ITP CCC
/PRINT=TWOTAIL NOSIG
/MISSING=PAIRWISE.

Correlations

		ROA	ROE	ACP	APP	ITP	CCC
ROA	Pearson Correlation	1	.173*	.189**	-.024	-.032	.204**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.010	.005	.728	.633	.002
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
ROE	Pearson Correlation	.173*	1	.424**	.335**	-.047	.423**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010		.000	.000	.487	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
ACP	Pearson Correlation	.189**	.424**	1	.800**	-.119	.999**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.000		.000	.078	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
APP	Pearson Correlation	-.024	.335**	.800**	1	-.120	.768**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.728	.000	.000		.076	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
ITP	Pearson Correlation	-.032	-.047	-.119	-.120	1	-.101
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.633	.487	.078	.076		.135
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220
CCC	Pearson Correlation	.204**	.423**	.999**	.768**	-.101	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.000	.000	.000	.135	
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	CCC, ACP, APP, ITP ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics	
					R Square Change	F Change
1	.364 ^a	.133	.117	.34440	.133	8.234

Model Summary

Model	Change Statistics		
	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	4 ^a	215	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), CCC, ACP, APP, ITP

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.907	4	.977	8.234	.000 ^b
	Residual	25.501	215	.119		
	Total	29.407	219			

- a. Dependent Variable: ROA
b. Predictors: (Constant), CCC, ACP, APP, ITP

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.653	.106		6.177	.000
	ACP	-.073	.041	-.133	-1.803	.073
	APP	-.201	.045	-.304	-4.456	.000
	ITP	-.022	.045	-.037	-.488	.626
	CCC	-.018	.030	-.044	-.619	.537

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	ACP	.744	1.344
	APP	.868	1.152
	ITP	.691	1.448
	CCC	.802	1.246

- a. Dependent Variable: ROA

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions			
				(Constant)	ACP	APP	ITP
1	1	4.153	1.000	.00	.01	.00	.00
	2	.655	2.518	.00	.00	.01	.00
	3	.099	6.483	.07	.66	.14	.02
	4	.062	8.197	.00	.33	.08	.92
	5	.031	11.593	.92	.00	.77	.05

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Variance Proportions
		CCC
1	1	.01
	2	.77
	3	.07
	4	.10
	5	.05

- a. Dependent Variable: ROA

REGRESSION

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	CCC, ACP, APP, ITP ^b	.	Enter

- a. Dependent Variable: ROE
 b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics	
					R Square Change	F Change
1	.340 ^a	.116	.099	.56517	.116	7.047

Model Summary

Model	Change Statistics		
	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	4 ^a	215	.000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), CCC, ACP, APP, ITP

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.004	4	2.251	7.047	.000 ^b
	Residual	68.674	215	.319		
	Total	77.678	219			

- a. Dependent Variable: ROE
 b. Predictors: (Constant), CCC, ACP, APP, ITP

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.170	.173		.979	.329
	ACP	-.134	.067	-.150	-2.011	.046
	APP	.284	.074	.264	3.842	.000
	ITP	-.186	.075	-.192	-2.491	.013
	CCC	.035	.049	.051	.717	.474

Coefficients^a

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	ACP	.744	1.344
	APP	.868	1.152
	ITP	.691	1.448

CCC	.802
-----	------

1.246

a. Dependent Variable: ROE

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions			
				(Constant)	ACP	APP	ITP
1	1	4.153	1.000	.00	.01	.00	.00
	2	.655	2.518	.00	.00	.01	.00
	3	.099	6.483	.07	.66	.14	.02
	4	.062	8.197	.00	.33	.08	.92
	5	.031	11.593	.92	.00	.77	.05

Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Variance Proportions	
		CCC	
1	1		.01
	2		.77
	3		.07
	4		.10
	5		.05

a. Dependent Variable: ROE